

Efficient trustworthy AI - making the best of data (AI, Data and Robotics Partnership)
(RIA)

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PANDORA

A Comprehensive Framework enabling the Delivery of
Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation

D6.1 Instantiation of PANDORA pipelines in industrial settings

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of Things
WP	Work Package
ADOA	Adaptive Distribution and Optimization of AI Inferencing in the Cloud-edge Computing Continuum
AlaaS	AI as a Service
CaaS	Computing as a Service
CAD	Computer-aided Design
CIM	Continual Inference Networks to Speed Up the Inference of DL Models
CRV	Self-validated, Causal, Robust, and Resilient Continuous Learning for Long-term Autonomy and Intelligence
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
DACL	Semi-automated Annotations, Labelling and Self-supervised Completion and Augmentation
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DEL	Leveraging Domain Knowledge for Explainable Learning
DICE	Domain-informed, Causal and Explainable AI Based on a Hybrid Learning Reasoning Approach for Continuous Learning
DL	Deep Learning
DRFEC	Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction Component
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
FL	Federated Learning
FRL	Federated Representational Learning
FRLM	Federated Representational Learning of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations
GENEOs	Group Equivariant Non-Expansive Operators
IM	Intent Manager
IoT	Internet of Things
LID	Local Intrinsic Dimensionality
ONNX	Open Neural Network Exchange
QU-MAD	Uncertainty Quantification Modelling and Development
SDG	Synthetic Data Generation
SPED	Spaces, People, Events, Devices
tSDG	Synthetic Data Generation for Time-series Data

UC	Use Case
V&V	Verification & Validation
vPLC	Virtual Programmable Logic Controller
vSDG	Synthetic Data Generation for Vision Data

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D6.1 - Instantiation of PANDORA pipelines in industrial settings) reports the work conducted in **Tasks 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3** during the first reporting period (M09-M18) of the PANDORA project within WP6 (Real-life experimentation to demonstrate scientific progress towards adopting trustworthy and energy-efficient AI systems). WP6 translates PANDORA's scientific advances into operational reality by instantiating AI-driven data pipelines across five heterogeneous industrial sectors.

The deliverable addresses three interconnected objectives:

Task 6.1 establishes the regulatory and organizational foundation by aligning business and validation scenarios across all five industrial pilots (FRA, SAG, HALCOR, PCL, and Ericsson) with PANDORA experimental protocols while ensuring compliance with GDPR and sector-specific data protection regulations. This task defines data acquisition mechanisms, execution plans, and stakeholder engagement strategies that enable systematic experimentation.

Task 6.2 creates detailed architectural blueprints that instantiate PANDORA data pipelines for each pilot use case. Through an innovative integrated approach, Tasks 6.1 and 6.2 have been unified into a comprehensive template structure that consolidates regulatory compliance specifications with technical pipeline architectures. Five complete pipeline blueprints have been developed, each defining data flows from acquisition through preprocessing, mining, discovering, modeling, and filtering, tailored to specific business sectors. These blueprints integrate core PANDORA components from Phase 1 (SDG, DACL, DEL, DRFE) and Phase 2 (FRLM, ADOA, CRV, DICE, CIM) with AlaaS, CaaS, and IM services to form modular, interoperable pipelines.

Task 6.3, led by NTUA, advanced ahead of schedule to establish verification and validation frameworks that systematically link KPIs to PANDORA strategies, components, and use case scenarios. The KPI mapping process ensures that both Phase 1 (trustworthy dataset generation) and Phase 2 (autonomous, energy-efficient AIoT operations) can be evaluated against defined benchmarks using appropriate metrics (Dunn's, Silhouette, Davies-Bouldin indexes for data quality, FL benchmarks like LEAF for federated learning, inference acceleration metrics for computing efficiency).

The integrated template approach represents a key innovation, enabling consistent documentation across heterogeneous industrial settings while maintaining the flexibility required for sector-specific adaptations. This modular framework supports the preparatory work for **Task 6.4** (operational deployment and experimentation) and **Task 6.5** (impact assessment), establishing the foundation for demonstrating PANDORA's applicability across multiple industrial sectors and validating its contribution to trustworthy, energy-efficient AI deployment in real-world AIoT systems.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to report the work conducted in Tasks 6.1, 6.2 of the PANDORA project, focusing on preparing and instantiating data pipelines for real-life industrial experimentation. These tasks aim to:

- i. Align business and validation scenarios across all five industrial pilots (SAG, EAB, PCL, FRA and HALCOR) in compliance with data protection regulations including GDPR and sector-specific requirements.
- ii. Instantiate PANDORA data pipelines by creating detailed architectural blueprints tailored to different business sectors, defining complete data flows from acquisition through processing, modeling, and inference.
- iii. Establish verification and validation frameworks that systematically link KPIs to PANDORA strategies, components, and use case scenarios, ensuring trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT operation.
- iv. Provide integrated documentation templates that consolidate regulatory compliance specifications with technical pipeline architectures, enabling consistent and efficient implementation across heterogeneous industrial settings.
- v. Define preparatory protocols for operational deployment, including data acquisition mechanisms, experimental execution plans, leveraging PANDORA core components and scenario adaptation for PANDORA in different phases of activities.

This deliverable documents the integrated approach developed to address Tasks 6.1 and 6.2 through a unified template structure, presents the complete data pipeline blueprints for each pilot use case, this data pipelines leverages from the PANDORA's core components, that is configured in a way where it aligns with business and validation scenarios (T6.1) to ensure both regulatory compliance with GDPR and sector-specific data protection requirements, and initiate the data pipeline by providing detailed architectural blueprints tailored to different UCs. and describes the verification and validation methodology established in coordination with Task 6.3 to ensure PANDORA's AI-driven pipelines are ready for real-world industrial validation and serve for PANDORA goal projects.

1.2 Intended readership

The intended audience of this document includes multiple partners participating across different work packages aligned with the objectives of Tasks 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3. This deliverable demonstrates how PANDORA core components were leveraged into data pipelines that ensure continual, energy efficient and autonomous AIoT systems at operation time. Every PANDORA component follows a different approach. Experts in AIoT can leverage the information provided in this document by using it for new innovative approaches.

PANDORA pilot owners and industrial partners (SAG, EAB, PCL, FRA and HALCOR, as referenced in T6.1 and T6.2) are primary beneficiaries, as they utilize the integrated templates and architectural blueprints to instantiate data pipelines within their operational environments, align business and validation scenarios with PANDORA experimental protocols, and ensure compliance with data protection regulations specific to their sectors.

Technology providers and component developers (Participants from T6.2 including IMT, AEGIS, STUBA, DIE, and those from WP3, WP4, and WP5) will use this document to understand how their components integrated and implemented within pilot-specific pipelines, adapt system modules for experimental execution, and ensure their implementations align with the complete data flow from acquisition through preparation, pre-processing, mining, discovering, modeling, and filtering as outlined in the blueprints.

Verification and validation teams (NTUA, AU, IMT, STUBA, CBRL, UNSPMF from T6.3) will reference this document to establish validation frameworks for both Phase 1 and Phase 2. They will utilize the documented verification and validation variables to assess performance against real datasets with ground truth information, physics laws, and domain knowledge, employing validity metrics and benchmarks to evaluate data quality, model explanations, inference acceleration, and implementation of the components capabilities across to pilots that realize Strategy 6.

Partners responsible for data acquisition and operational configuration (T5.1 participants) will benefit from the documented data acquisition mechanisms, defines relevant technical, organizational, legal (GDPR) and commercial aspects of data sharing to the consortium. Moreover, they investigate the availability of relevant assets in external open-source platforms aiming to enhance those developed by the consortium. and execution time plans that support efficient experimental setup across all pilots.

Dissemination and communication teams (T7.2 and T7.4 participants) will leverage this document to engage stakeholders from the wider scientific and industrial community outside the consortium, demonstrating how the integrated template approach and architectural blueprints serve as reusable knowledge assets for industrial AI deployment.

The PANDORA framework will benefit from sector-tailored data pipeline blueprints created for each use case, which addresses regulatory compliance, component interoperability, and cross-disciplinary collaboration challenges in heterogeneous industrial settings. The framework provides tracking of state for the implementation of the PANODRA core components with clear validation approaches for both design-time trustworthy datasets and runtime autonomous AIoT operations.

1.3 Relationship with other PANDORA WPs and managerial organization

Work within WP6 is directly connected to **Objective 4**: Provide a cross-sector and multi-variant smart data space to realize the PANDORA framework and validate the data-enabled trustworthy AI mechanisms in real life scenarios. Specifically, this deliverable addresses Enablers EN4.1 (Definition of real-life experiments demonstrating trustworthy AI-enhanced data pipelines) and EN4.2 (Specification of domain specific methodological approach and relevant experimentation variables).

The architectural foundations developed in WP2 (particularly T2.4 and T2.5) have been used to define the generic PANDORA architecture and requirements framework that underpins the pipeline blueprints instantiated in this deliverable. The use case descriptions, requirement categorizations (business–data–user), and trial scenarios established in T2.5 directly inform the business and validation scenario alignment conducted in T6.1, contributing to KPI4.1.1 (Number of scenario variations defined per domain ≥ 2).

The trustworthy datasets and data augmentation methods generated in WP3 (through components such as SDG) are mapped within the pipeline blueprints as Phase 1 components, providing the foundational data preparation and enhancement capabilities required for each pilot's specific operational context to support trustworthy AI-enhanced data pipelines.

The AI methods, techniques, and services developed in WP4 form core components integrated within the Phase 2 runtime pipelines documented in this deliverable. These include CRV (Continuous Learning), DICE (Domain-informed Explainable AI), FRLM (Federated Representational Learning), CIM (Continual Inference Networks), and ADOA (Adaptive Distribution and Optimization of AI Inferencing), which enable trustworthy, robust, continual, and energy-efficient AIoT operations across the computing continuum as specified in the pilot-specific architectural blueprints.

1.4 Structure

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the different pilot use cases in the PANDORA project highlighting business context, operational environment and an understanding of the contributing strategies to the specific use case. Section 3 provides an insight on the pipelines per strategy along with the generic pipeline per component. Section 4 is targeted to a pipeline adaptation per scenario with a blueprint overview that includes decomposed sequence diagrams with the PANDORA components. Section 5 includes a scenario specific pipeline adaptation in order to be able to track any occurring changes. Section 6 includes a validation plan linked to task 6.3 that enables a validation plan, ending with section 7 for a conclusion.

2 Use case contexts

This section introduces the different pilot use cases in the PANDORA project highlighting with a detailed highlight on its business context, the different operational environment and an understanding of the contributing strategies to the specific use case. The purpose of this section is to give better understanding to the project different pilot cases, how they differ in requirement structure, which provides motivation in the following section to understand how the generic pipeline can be adapted across the different UCs.

The following tables (1-15) highlight the context of the use case and its goals in regard to its scenarios and leveraged PANDORA components:

KPI table

- KPI
- Relative scenario of the Use case
- Descriptive text
Requirement Table
- Requirements
- Scenario Id
- Requirement description
Table of contributing strategies
- Component (defining component along its corresponding strategy)
- Identifying the phase
- Explaining purpose for the UC

2.1 SAG sector overview

Siemens Industrial Edge (IE) is an open, ready-to-use edge computing platform with edge devices, edge applications (apps), and connectivity through an integrated app and device management infrastructure. It allows customers to easily connect, manage, and operate globally distributed edge installations, using their own or marketplace apps. Once set up, data flows seamlessly across the IE value chain. Predicting failures with technologies like artificial intelligence enables optimized maintenance planning, increased reliability, and minimized downtimes. Using manufacturing plant data, customers or OEM vendors can focus attention where needed to prevent outages, increase availability, enable precise maintenance, and reduce downtime.

2.1.1 Operational environment

HW:

- Siemens IPC 1047E
- ET200
- Routed IP network
- Conveyor belt
- Light barrier
- Network camera
- Arm sorter

SW:

- Siemens Industrial Edge
- Siemens SIMATIC S7 vPLC
- AI inference server app
Grafana

2.1.2 Data requirements

Data source:

- Server Machines
- Physical environment (conveyor systems, cameras)
- Network devices (switches, routers)
- vPLC and ET200 systems

Data type:

- Compute metrics
- Network metrics
- Physical process metrics
- Network device metrics

2.1.3 Key requirements

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 represent respectively, the different KPIs defined for the SAG use case for each scenario, the user requirements along with previously defined strategies that contribute to the UC for each scenario.

Table 1: SAG KPI table

KPI ID	Scenario ID	Description	Target
KPI1.1.2	UC1S1, UC1S2	Number of models trained	>= 10
KPI1.2.1	UC1S1	Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction	15%
KPI1.2.2	UC1S1	Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem	> 1
KPI1.5.1	UC1S1, UC1S2	Number of models trained	>= 3
KPI1.5.2	UC1S1, UC1S2	Decrease in data redundancy (Dimensionality reduction)	>= 50 %
KPI2.1.1	UC1S1, UC1S2	Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces	20%
KPI2.2.1	UC1S1, UC1S2	Increased modules accuracy	20%
KPI2.2.2	UC1S1, UC1S2	Reduction in model execution time	20%
KPI2.2.3	UC1S1, UC1S2	Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data	> 15%
KPI2.3.1	UC1S1, UC1S2	Increased accuracy levels of real-time observations to capture out-of-distribution events	20%
KPI2.3.2	UC1S1, UC1S2	Number of models deployed across the cloud continuum	>= 3
KPI2.4.1	UC1S1	Improved quality of the understandability related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions	20%
KPI3.1.1	UC1S1, UC1S2	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	15%
KPI3.1.2	UC1S2, UC1S1	Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics	70%

Table 2: SAG Requirement table

Scenario ID	Requirement	Requirement description	Priority level
UC1S1	UR1	PANDORA framework produces synthetic data based on a simulated environment to train AI models (T3.1)	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework provides an AI model to predict network outages and critical situations (T4.1, T4.4)	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework outputs explanations (T3.3, T4.2) as well as uncertainty assessments (T3.2) alongside predictions	May
	UR4	PANDORA framework is able to support the distributed / federated learning of the AI model as well as its inference (T4.3, T4.5, T5.4).	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework can gather and process data from various sources to ensure that the necessary information is available for training and evaluating AI models (T5.1).	May
	UR6	PANDORA framework can use methods to identify and keep only the most important data information, which helps improve the accuracy, understanding, and efficiency of AI models (T3.5).	Should
UC1S2	UR1	PANDORA framework produces synthetic data based on a simulated environment to train AI models (T3.1)	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides an AI model to predict network outages and critical situations(T4.1, T4.4)	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework should support the distributed / federated learning of the AI model as well as its inference (T4.3, T4.5, T5.4).	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework can gather and process data from various sources to ensure that the necessary information is available for training and evaluating AI models (T5.1).	May
	UR6	PANDORA framework can use methods to identify and keep only the most important data information, which helps improve the accuracy, understanding, and efficiency of AI models (T3.5).	Should

Table 3: SAG Contributing strategies per scenario table

Component (Strategy number)	Phase	UC1S1	UC1S2	Purpose for Partner
tSDG (1)	1	✓	✓	Generate synthetic time-series datasets
QU-MAD (2)	1	✓	X	Extract, quantify, and communicate the uncertainties for minimizing false positive and false negatives
DEL (3)	1	✓	X	Detect critical situations, providing an explanation why

DRFE (5)	1	✓	✓	Provide dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction while retaining the most essential data information
CRV (7)	2	✓	✓	Continual learning of AIoT predictive models needed for intent driven networking performance
FRLM (8)	2	✓	✓	Federated Learning representations will be used to create models forming compact data representations and unsupervised anomaly detection models
DICE (9)	2	✓	X	Provide explainability with domain informed data of the 5G configuration
CIM (10)	2	✓	✓	Provide efficient, frame-by-frame classification or regression for sequence data
ADOA (11)	2	✓	✓	Split Computing and Distributed Computing techniques will be used to provide efficient computations

2.2 EAB sector Overview

A 5G enabled smart building with smart IoT sensors, AI-enabled robotic helpers, and edge infrastructure. The EAB use case focuses on safe communication-aware robot planning and closed loop control to ensure trustworthy 5G connectivity in dynamic environments. The robot uses AI-planning or other applicable techniques to ensure (i) speed, (ii) specific 5G throughput/latency observed, and (iii) collision with obstacles preventions. In addition, it could be possible to change the amount/quality of sensing updates to reduce network load.

2.2.1 Operational Environment

HW:

- Robot with associated sensors and actuators
- 5G antennas and base stations
- Edge server

SW:

- ROS
- Robot controller
- AI based robot path planner
- AI based communication scheduler

2.2.2 Data requirements

Data source:

- Robot sensors and ROS software
- 5G performance measure counters
- MAP/ domain knowledge of the environment

Data type:

- Robot sensing data (Lidar,odometry, camera)
- Robot SLAM data
- 5G dataset such as signal strength
- Domain knowledge of environment via mapping in JSON files format

2.2.3 Key Requirements

Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6 below represent respectively, the different KPIs defined for the EAB use case for each scenario, along with previously defined strategies that contribute to the UC for each scenario.

Table 4: EAB KPI table

KPI ID	Scenario ID	Description	Target
KPI1.1.1	UC2S1	Increase models accuracy	20%
KPI1.3.1	UC2S1, UC2S2	Increase labelling and annotation accuracy	20%
KPI1.3.2	UC2S1	The number of predictive models achieving better performance after labelling and annotation	>=3
KPI1.3.3	UC2S1	Reduce human interventions	50%
KPI1.4.1	UC2S1	Decrease periodic human inspections on models	20%
KPI2.2.1	UC2S1, UC2S2	Increased model accuracy	20%
KPI2.2.2	UC2S1, UC2S2	Reduction in model execution time	20%
KPI2.2.3	UC2S1, UC2S2	Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data	>15%
KPI2.4.1	UC2S2	Improved quality of the understandability-related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions.	>20%
KPI3.1.3	UC2S1	Decrease in the response time for AI models inference	>=20%
KPI3.3.1	UC2S1, UC2S2	Improvement of model re- training time	>=10%

Table 5: EAB Requirement table

Scenario ID	Requirement	Requirement description	Priority level
UC2S1	UR1	PANDORA framework is able to generalize datasets across new terrains and/or obstacles	Should
	UR2	PANDORA framework can generate synthetic datasets with the necessary semantic information	Should
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides verification that the generated dataset for robot navigation reflects realistic scenarios	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework is able to use the validated dataset for obstacle avoidance and/or planning purposes	Shall
	UR5	PANDORA framework utilizes a federation of robots to detect anomalous behavior or intent issues	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework is able to generate missing data and annotations on the raw dataset	May
	UR7	PANDORA framework deploys the models using split or distributed computing topologies for efficiency	May

	UR8	The system must implement access control mechanisms to verify and authenticate users (actors) before granting access to PANDORA's resources.	Should
UC2S2	UR1	PANDORA framework is able to employ synthetic datasets that capture variations in multiple factors (such as obstacles, antenna position)	Should
	UR2	PANDORA framework can verify the validity of the synthetic dataset that are aimed to capture variations caused by multiple factors (such as obstacles, antenna position)	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides accurate predictions for possible deviations in 5G throughput and latency	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework is able to incorporate predictions into models that guide autonomous actions over the 5G network	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework is able to provide intuitive explanations for AI-based autonomous decisions	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework is able to generate missing data and annotations on the raw dataset	May
	UR7	PANDORA framework deploys the models using split or distributed computing topologies for efficiency	May
	UR8	PANDORA framework will implement access control mechanisms to verify and authenticate users (actors) before granting access to PANDORA's resources.	Should

Table 6: EAB Contributing strategies table

Component (Strategy number)	Phase	UC2S1	UC2S2	Purpose for Partner
tSDG (1)	1	✓	✓	Generate synthetic time-series datasets
DACL (4)	1	✓	✓	Impute missing values or annotate dataset with symbolic knowledge
FRLM (8)	2	✓	X	Federated Learning representations will be used to create models forming compact data
CRV (7)	2	X	✓	Continual learning of AIoT predictive models needed for intent driven networking performance
DICE (9)	2	x	✓	Provide physics-informed explanations for path planning or uncertainty quantification for QoS measures prediction.
ADOA (11)	2	✓	✓	Split Computing and Distributed Computing techniques will be used to provide efficient computations

2.3 PCL sector Overview

Visual inspection tasks to ensure required quality standards of manufactured goods are currently mostly performed manually. PCL seeks to fully automate these activities by training and deploying AI models using product images and incorporating these technologies into the production processes. PCL is currently facing problems creating the right datasets with sufficient accuracy (as benchmarked by human performance) due to insufficient real image data of defective products. To reduce the lead time for new automated visual inspection systems, synthetic image data will be created based on a limited sample of real images, taken with a physical camera setup, from a shaver part & design that needs to be inspected.

2.3.1 Operational Environment

HW:

- Frame for demonstrator (already available)
- Lens (add lens type)
- Camera (Basler acA2440-20gc)
- Carrier for the ink jetted product (chest)
- Light dome (HPD2-250FC)
- Server and data storage for images and inference of AI model
- Printed shaver products (chest in colours Adriatic and Champagne Gold, with print in PCL and Norelco version, good and bad products with all failure types)

SW:

- Python (Pytorch, Tensorflow, Keras, OpenCV, Sci-kit learn)
- MLFlow
- Kubernetes framework for model inference
- Production data

2.3.2 Data requirements

Data source:

- High quality product image dataset of shaver chests from Basler camera per quality category (good, interrupted print, fingerprint, print position wrong, smudged)
- (3D) CAD files of shaver chests
- Graphical design files of print designs
- MES system for production data

Data type:

- PNG-format from scenario1
- 1200x1400, 96 dpi, 24 bits
- CAD file of the shaver chests (3D geometry)
- STP file
- Product Graphic Design in PDF format
- If needed, ISI files which contain graphic designs and direct input for the printer
- Production data on product quality (input from scenario 1 should be used)

2.3.3 Key Requirements

Table 7, Table 8 and Table 9 below represent respectively, the different KPIs defined for the PCL use case for each scenario, along with previously defined strategies that contribute to the UC for each scenario.

Table 7: PCL KPI table

KPI ID	Scenario ID	Description	Target
KPI 1.2.1	UC3S1, UC3S2	Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction	15%
KPI 1.2.2	UC3S1, UC3S2	Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem	>1
KPI 1.3.2	UC3S1, UC3S2	The number of predictive models achieving better performance after labelling and annotation	>=3
KPI 1.3.3	UC3S1, UC3S2	Reduce human interventions	50%
KPI 1.4.1	UC3S2	Decrease periodic human inspections on models	20%
KPI 2.2.1	UC3S1, UC3S2	Increase models accuracy	20%
KPI 2.2.2	UC3S1, UC3S2	Reduction in model execution time	20%
KPI 2.2.3	UC3S1, UC3S2	Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data	15%
KPI 3.1.1	UC3S1, UC3S2	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	15%
KPI 3.3.1	UC3S1, UC3S2	Improvement of model re-training time	10%
KPI 3.3.2	UC3S1, UC3S2	Increase of model validation cycles	20%

Table 8: PCL requirement table

Scenario ID	Requirement	Requirement description	Priority level
UC3S1	UR1	PANDORA framework provides a scalable and flexible image creation process to produce synthetic data.	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework requires as input a limited sample of a X<50 images captured from a physical camera setup (demonstrator) to generate an accurate synthetic dataset.	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework generates images that contain all failure types as provided by the PCL team.	May
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides annotated synthetic image datasets	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework provides models that can handle multiple background colors and graphic print designs.	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework can be supported by PCL (for example, Python source code)	Should
	UR7	PANDORA framework will give insight into the defect types of real images (which can be used for making a pareto)	May
UC3S2	UR1	PANDORA framework provides a scalable and flexible image creation process to produce synthetic data	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework requires as input a limited sample of a X<50 images captured from a physical camera setup (demonstrator) to generate an accurate synthetic dataset. Difference with scenario1 is that these images will be from another graphical design (so in this case the Adriatic blue chest, while synthetic	Shall

		images from the champagne gold chest have to be created)	
	UR3	PANDORA framework generates images that contain all failure types as provided by the PCL team	May
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides annotated synthetic image datasets	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework provides models that can handle multiple background colors and graphic print designs	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework can be supported by PCL (for example, Python source code)	Should
	UR7	PANDORA framework is able to generate synthetic image data based on CAD drawings/3D models	Shall

Table 9: PCL contributing strategies table

Component (Strategy number)	Phase	UC3S1	UC3S2	Purpose for PCL
vSDG (1)	1	✓	✓	Generate synthetic image data from a limited dataset of real product image data
QU-MAD (2)	1	✓	✓	Quantify uncertainty in quality predictions to reduce false positives and improve decision-making reliability
CRV (7)	2	✓	✓	Continuous learning of the model using image data of new unforeseen faults, allowing it to adjust to changing operational circumstances

2.3.4 Privacy/Confidentiality/Cybersecurity requirements

Data Protection:

- Data Minimization: Only product and manufacturing data collected, no personal information
- Anonymization: No personally identifiable information (PII) in datasets
- Access Controls: Role-based access control (RBAC) for different user types:
 - Operators: Read-only access to data and results
 - Maintenance/Engineering: Access only to their specific component data
 - IT: Full access
- NDA’s for users: Limit sharing of business sensitive data: CAD-files

Cybersecurity Measures:

- Network Segmentation:
- Isolated OT network for critical PLC systems
- DMZ for external access
- Software screening before deploying on local servers

2.4 FRA sector overview

The hydrogen refueling infrastructure for public transportation, specifically supporting bus fueling operations. Under the Covalion brand (FRA), expert teams develop hydrogen refueling stations as critical infrastructure requiring high reliability, functional safety, and cybersecurity resilience, some of the stations serves up to 100-120 buses per day with a target refueling time of 5-8 minutes per vehicle.

2.4.1 Operational Environment

HW:

- Main Physical Components:
 - Compressors: 2 (10RHM11, 10RHM12, 10RHM14)
 - Hydrogen compression from trailer delivery (200-300 bar) to storage pressure (500 bar)
- Storage Tanks:
 - High-pressure tanks: 500 bar, 1.7 Nm³ each (HD-1 to HD-4)
 - 2 Low-pressure tanks: 50 bar, 95 Nm³, 350 kg each (ND-1, ND-2)
- Dispensers: 2
- Sensor Infrastructure (200+ sensors):
 - 13 Temperature Transmitters (TT): -40°C to +50°C range
 - 14 Pressure Transmitters (PT): 0-600 bar range
 - 13 Pressure Indicators (PI)
 - Flow Transmitters (FT)
 - 76 Valve position indicators (binary: open/closed)

SW:

- TIA Portal (Siemens) - PLC programming environment
- WinMOD - Digital Twin simulation (in development)
- HMI/SCADA - Local monitoring interface

2.4.2 Data requirements

Data source:

- PLC-generated real-time sensor data
- Covalion operational database (HRS)
- Alarm logs

Data type:

- Numeric data: Temperature, pressure, flow
- Binary data: Valve positions

Data format:

- CSV files

2.4.3 Key Requirements

The tables below, Table 10, Table 11 and Table 12 represent respectively, the different KPIs defined for the FRA use case for each scenario, along with previously defined strategies that contribute to the UC for each scenario.

Table 10: FRA KPI table

KPI ID	Scenario ID	Description	Target
KPI1.2.1	UC4S1, UC4S2	Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction	15%
KPI1.3.2	UC4S1	The number of predictive models achieving better performance after labelling and annotation	≥3
KPI1.5.1	UC4S1	Number of models trained	≥3
KPI2.1.1	UC4S1, UC4S2	Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces	20%
KPI2.4.1	UC4S1	Number of improved properties characterizing the quality of the provided explanations of continuous and domain-informed AI decisions	≥2
KPI3.1.2	UC4S1, UC4S2	Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics	+70%

Table 11: FRA Requirement table

Scenario ID	Requirement	Requirement description	Priority Level
UC4S1	UR1	PANDORA framework detects operational anomalies in HRS components early using time series data and error logs.	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework is able to predict potential component failures or shutdowns in advance to enhance safety and reliability.	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework is able to identify anomalies with an accuracy of 80%.	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework will provide metrics to evaluate performance against KPIs, including anomaly detection and prediction accuracy.	Shall
	UR5	PANDORA framework would facilitate anomaly detection by providing contextual data for experts to address and confirm identified anomalies.	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework helps ensure the model provides explainable outputs, allowing users to understand the rationale behind anomaly detection and predictions.	Should
UC4S2	UR1	PANDORA framework will be retrained periodically using updated datasets acquired ensuring continuous improvement in detection accuracy and robustness	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework allows domain experts to validate detected anomalies and integrate their feedback in the model	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides a functional element of reducing false positives by refining the anomaly detection model based on experts' insight	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework continuously monitors and report on key performance metrics, such as anomaly detection accuracy and false positive rates, to track and guide model improvements	Shall

	UR5	PANDORA framework automatically schedules and execute model retraining at defined intervals or when performance metrics indicate the need for improvement	Should
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Table 12: FRA Contributing strategies table

Component (Strategy number)	Phase	UC4S1	UC4S2	Purpose for FRA
QU-MAD(2)	1	✓	✓	Quantify uncertainty in anomaly predictions to reduce false positives and improve decision-making reliability
DEL(3)	1	✓	✓	Incorporate domain knowledge (physical laws, safety constraints, or time constraints) for causal explanations
DACL(4)	1	✓	X	Impute missing values and anomaly labels
DRFE(5)	2	✓	X	Provide dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction while retaining the most essential data information
CRV(7)	2	✓	X	Enable Survival Analysis model construction for time-dependent, multi-event time series data.
DICE(9)	2	✓	X	Provide counterfactual explanations on survival analysis predictions to give insights to the expert on how to postpone a failure.

2.4.4 Privacy/Confidentiality/Cybersecurity requirements

Data Protection:

- Data Minimization: Only operational sensor data collected, no personal information about bus drivers or station operators
- Anonymization: No Personally Identifiable Information (PII) in datasets
- Access Controls: Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) for different user types:
 - Station Operators: Read-only access to monitoring dashboards
 - Maintenance Staff: Access to historical data and diagnostic tools
 - Remote Maintenance (suppliers): Least-privilege access only to their specific component data

Cybersecurity Measures:

- Network Segmentation:
 - Isolated OT network for critical PLC systems
 - DMZ for external access
 - Separate network for IT/monitoring systems

2.5 HALCOR sector overview

HALCOR is the copper and alloys extrusion division of ELVALHALCOR S.A. HALCOR Tubes Plant in Greece occupies 350 people and has significant expertise in copper tubes manufacturing. It produces approximately 80.000 tons of copper tubes per year. It is the largest plant of its type in Europe. The production process of these tubes consists of a number of discrete production steps. The entry point is the creation of a single 'mother' tube from a heated billet (large solid cylinder) through an extrusion with hydraulic press. These tubes have a length of 15 to 30 m which are then reduced in diameter and wall thickness by either drawing or cold rolling. Further reductions are then performed at Breakdown lines and Spinner Blocks by drawing the tube further with successive passes till the final or semi-final dimension is reached. The tubes can be finished either with a smooth inner surface or with a grooved integral enhanced inner surface in numerous profiles. The final dimensions and form of the tube, either coiled or straightened in lengths, are then given in finishing lines. Further processing, if required, can be performed, such as degreasing, annealing, cutting to shorter lengths, insulating with PE foam and sheathing with plastic coating. The final step of production is the packaging and the storing of the tubes.

2.5.1 Operational environment

HW:

- PLC analyser (sensor data, fine granularity)

SW:

- Plant's Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system
- Energy Monitoring System (PME)
- Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system
- Manufacturing Execution System (MES)
- PLC analyzer (data analysis software)
- Advanced reporting tools

2.5.2 Data requirements

Data source:

- Plant's Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system
- Manufacturing Execution System (MES) (fault/status-related data, human entered data, coarse-grained)
- Energy Monitoring System
- Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system
- PLC analyzer (sensor data, fine granularity)
- Advanced reporting tools
- Production plan logs

Data type:

- ERP data
- Fault/status-related data
- Human entered data
- Coarse-grained data
- Sensor data (fine granularity)
- Analytical data
- Energy consumption data
- Production plans

2.5.3 Key Requirements

Table 13, Table 14 and Table 15 below represent respectively, the different KPIs defined for the HALCOR use case for each scenario, along with previously defined strategies that contribute to the UC for each scenario.

Table 13: HALCOR KPI table

KPI ID	Scenario ID	Description	Target
KPI1.1.2	UC5S1, UC5S2	Number of models trained	>=10
KPI1.2.1	UC5S1	Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction	15%
KPI1.2.2	UC5S1	Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem	>=1
KPI1.5.1	UC5S1, UC5S2	Number of models trained	>= 3
KPI1.5.2	UC5S1, UC5S2	Decrease in data redundancy (Dimensionality reduction)	>= 50%
KPI2.2.1	UC5S1	Increase model accuracy	>=20%
KPI2.2.3	UC5S1	Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data	>=15%
KPI2.4.1	UC5S1	Number of improved properties characterizing the quality of the provided explanations of continuous and domain-informed AI decisions	>=2
KPI3.1.1	UC5S1, UC5S2	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	15%
KPI3.1.3	UC5S1, UC5S2	Decrease in the response time for AI models' inference	20%

Table 14: HALCOR requirement table

Scenario ID	Requirement	Requirement description	Priority level
UC4S1	UR1	PANDORA framework provides accurate and timely predictions, within specified error margins, across various time frames (e.g., next hour, day, etc.), with results generated in real-time or within a few seconds.	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework provides that models remain reliable over different time frames and operational conditions, and its algorithms shall be updated regularly to reflect changes in operations and environment.	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides an easy to navigate user interface with a feedback mechanism on input data validity, and report prediction processing status	Should
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides an analysis of reasons for deviations in energy consumption predictions, highlighting factors that contribute to unexpected variations and supporting users in understanding prediction outcomes.	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework provides a mechanism for users to give feedback on the system's predictions and	Should

		usability.	
	UR6	PANDORA framework is able to create benchmarks for optimal energy performance and generate automated alerts for significant deviations, failures, or anomalies	Should
	UR7	PANDORA framework is able to identify and prioritize the most relevant features and data sources that contribute to accurate energy consumption predictions, reducing data processing time and enhancing model explainability	May
	UR8	PANDORA framework provides real-time monitoring of the press's consumption, displaying current data and trends	Should
	UR9	PANDORA framework provides detailed reports that include predicted energy consumption, variance from typical consumption, and confidence intervals	Shall
UC4S2	UR1	PANDORA framework provides accurate and timely predictions, within specified error margins, across various time frames (e.g., next hour, day, etc.), with results generated in real-time or within a few seconds.	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework provides an easy-to-use interface for users to define prediction windows, production plans, and other relevant parameters efficiently	Should
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides an easy to navigate user interface with a feedback mechanism on input data validity, and report prediction processing status	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides an analysis of reasons for deviations in energy consumption predictions, highlighting factors that contribute to unexpected variations and supporting users in understanding prediction outcomes.	Shall
	UR5	PANDORA framework provides a mechanism for users to give feedback on the system's predictions and usability.	May
	UR6	PANDORA framework is able to create benchmarks for optimal energy performance and generate automated alerts for significant deviations, failures, or anomalies	Shall
	UR7	PANDORA framework is able to identify and prioritize the most relevant features and data sources that contribute to accurate energy consumption predictions, reducing data processing time and enhancing model explainability	Should
	UR8	PANDORA framework provides real-time monitoring of the press's consumption, displaying current data and trends	Should

	UR9	PANDORA framework provides detailed reports that include predicted energy consumption, variance from typical consumption, and confidence intervals	May
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Table 15: HALCOR Contributing strategies table

Component (Strategy number)	Phase	UC4S1	UC4S2	Purpose for Partner
tSDG (1)	1	✓	X	Provide synthetic time-series data
QU-MAD (2)	1	✓	X	Provide uncertainty quantification to assess confidence in energy consumption predictions
DEL (3)	1	✓	X	Provide causal explanations in the form of causal, optimal feature subspaces
DACL (4)	1	✓	✓	Imputes missing values and labels
DRFE (5)	1	✓	✓	Provide dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction while retaining the most essential data information
CRV (7)	2	✓	X	Continuously trains energy prediction model
DICE (9)	2	✓	X	Use causal feature subspaces to globally explain the predictions.
CIM (10)	2	✓	✓	Provide efficient next time step forecasting for the specific task

3 Generic pipeline and pipeline per strategy

3.1 Generic pipelines

Figure 1: Phase 2 component diagram

The generic pipeline refers to the common process for Phase 2 that is specified for handling data and ML models through the core PANDORA components:

- AlaaS
- CaaS
- IM (Information manager)

The use of the “Generic Pipeline” is efficient, as it can be easily adopted and applied across all different use case scenarios. Figure 1 above represents the main sub-components within AlaaS and rest of PANDORA core components. Leveraging the customizable and trustworthy datasets produced at PANDORA design-time, superior training of multiple models may be done across a variety of models (e.g. continual learning, federated learning).

The implementation involves the deployment processes and model tracking (MLFlow), and secure API-based communication between components. Data and ML models are exchanged in standardized formats (e.g., JSON for metadata) and may undergo transformation such as feature encoding or compression before used by other components.

The key in this part is to focus on the implementation of the generic pipeline. For each use case, a table will be provided describing the interactions between AlaaS, CaaS, and IM, along with the specific roles of each component. The tables below (Table 16-20) fields included are:

- **Components:** This column organizes the different components rather than grouping them all, to address the deliverable requirements to focus on the interaction between the specific components.
- **Description:** Brief description of how each component fits the overall flow.

- **Detailed tools:** In this column, tools used can be displayed to include all used and leveraged tools, as it can help give an understanding of the implementation process.
- **Input/Output:** This helps distinguish between raw data or the used trained model.
- **Dependencies:** It can help outline how some components rely on each other, which helps to provide an understanding of the pipeline structure.

After a trained model is selected, PANDORA proposes the implementation of parallel data pipelines that ensure continual, energy efficient and autonomous AIoT systems at operation time. Every PANDORA component follows a different approach. CRV considers input domain knowledge (from Phase 1) and unseen uncertainties of the smart space ecosystems such as unpredictable faults, errors and adversarial attacks. Another learning data pipeline will be implemented by relying on the FRLM component for handling massive data acquisitions and large-scale simulations. Regarding the support of explainable AI inference as a service, PANDORA provides three novel approaches, grouped under the DICE component. The CIM component uses Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DNN through Continual processing of input streams. A representation of the available IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum will be modeled to provide (near) real-time operation on low computational power processors. Finally, the ADOA component supports efficient inference of DNN by exploiting the different capabilities in the IoT-Edge/Fog-Cloud continuum. This will be achieved through split computing and/or distributed computing)

3.1.1 Generic pipeline SAG

Table 16 focuses on the interaction between AlaaS, CaaS, and IM and the specific interactions of the other PANDORA core components within the use case of SAG and its roles of the different components. It also provides vital information on the components used tools, along with detailed information regarding the input and output date, by also highlighting any dependencies or changes withing the component per use case.

Table 16: SAG Generic pipeline table

Component	Description and role	Tools	Input data/Models	Output data/Models	Dependencies
AlaaS	Manages the entire AI lifecycle and has the following sub-components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model registry • Model selector • Model lifecycle manager • Model inferencing • Model Re-training 	Model registry: MLFlow Model selection: Graph and meta-model search over MLflow Model lifecycle management: Meta-model-based drift detection	Trained models, time series data, synthetic data (Phase 1)	Selected, optimized and deployed models for inference	CaaS (resources)

CaaS	Provides the necessary computational resources for training and inferencing. It acts as the resource provider for the AlaaS	Benchmarking tools Queueing models Reinforcement learning algorithms	Resource requirements from AlaaS	Computational resources	AlaaS
IM	Converts user intents to goals	3GPP schema template. Python based goal generator	User provided intents	User interface	Non
tSDG	Generates realistic and customizable datasets for AIoT model training through event-driven simulations of time-series data	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as PyTorch, pandas, NumPy, and scikit.	Time series IoT datasets and domain expert knowledge in CSV format.	A realistic synthetic dataset consisting of time-series data across devices, network, and app layers in CSV format.	DAACL & DRFEC components
QU-MAD	Extract, quantify, and communicate the uncertainties from data and AI models in AIoT systems using Bayesian and Ensemble approaches. Additionally, it incorporates a user-feedback mechanism to annotate and adapt based on user trust, ultimately improving AI model performance and trustworthiness.	Python 3.9 or more, ML frameworks and libraries (PyTorch, Lightning GDAL, Gradio, ...)	Raw data from AIoT system; synthetic generated data	Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback	tSDG, DAACL
DRFE	Provides dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction while	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-	Time series IoT datasets in CSV format.	Processed data with reduced dimensions and complexity,	No

	retaining the most essential data information	learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, pandas, NumPy		along with metrics quantifying the reduction and complexity. The metrics are optional. The output will be either .csv or Json	
DEL	Using the knowledge of AIoT experts, the module aims to develop explainable AI models, based on geometrical symmetries, to detect critical situations in the scenario (i.e., network bandwidth saturation)	Python 3.9+, scientific computation libraries, ML libraires, Python libraries	Time/Data series, domain knowledge (rules, knowledge graphs), learning tasks	Libraries of GENEOS and/or causal structures	tSDG, DACL
FRLM	This component aims to enable federated (representational) learning (FRL) within the PANDORA ecosystem. It consists of two main parts: the FRL server and the FRL Edge	Python with libraries and frameworks such as pandas, NumPy, scikit-learn, Keras and flwr	Datasets uploaded from edge devices and configuration inputs for the FL training component	A global data representation model that can be exploited for outlier detection in unsupervised learning settings and for classification in supervised learning settings	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism
ADOA	The component dynamically adjusts deep learning (DL) models to fit specific application requirements and resource constraints, optimizing for factors like inference time, accuracy, resource	Python libraries, e.g., Pytorch	ONNX format for DL model description, graph or topology models for infrastructure specification	Optimized DL model solutions including splitting, pruning, quantization, or early-exit approaches	CaaS,AlaaS

	usage, and energy consumption without retraining the model				
CRV	Phase 2 software component for continuous learning of AIoT predictive models	Python with industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, pandas).	Continuously delivered training tabular/time-series datasets structured as sequences of learning tasks	Predictive regression models	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism, AlaaS: AI model registry
DICE	The component focuses on providing explainability for AIoT systems after the inference phase.	Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.	Data (e.g., time series, data series); domain knowledge (e.g., rules, knowledge graphs); predictive models; data point/series to explain	Explanations including feature subsets, causal explanations, libraries of Geneos	tSDG, CRV, FRL, CIM, DEL, AlaaS: AI model registry, CaaS
CIM	The component provides efficient, frame-by-frame classification or regression for sequence data, such as image sequences or time-series streams, enabling low-latency and high-throughput inference for AIoT systems.	Python with industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, pandas).	Image sequence stream (images in PNG/Jpeg/Raw format); time series (sensor recording streams in binary format formed by data frames of duration 1, 0.5, 0.1, etc. seconds, depending on the use case requirements), network video stream (RTSP).	Classification or regression results in real-time with each frame or snippet of input data.	AlaaS

3.1.2 Generic pipeline EAB

Table 17 below focuses on the interaction between AlaaS, CaaS, and IM and the specific interactions of the other PANDORA core components within the use case of EAB and its roles of the different components. It also provides vital information on the components used tools, along with detailed information regarding the input and output data, by also highlighting any dependencies or changes withing the component per use case.

Table 17: EAB Generic pipeline table

Component	Description and role	Tools	Input data/Models	Output data/Models	Dependencies
AlaaS	<p>Manages the entire AI lifecycle and has the following sub-components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model registry • Model selector • Model lifecycle manager • Model inferencing <p>Model Re-training</p>	<p>Model registry: MLFlow</p> <p>Model selection: Graph and meta-model search over MLflow</p> <p>Model lifecycle management: Meta-model-based drift detection</p>	Trained models, time series data, synthetic data (Phase 1)	Selected, optimized, Selected, optimized and deployed models for inference	CaaS (resources)
CaaS	Provides the necessary computational resources for training and inferencing. It acts as the resource provider for the AlaaS.	<p>Benchmarking tools</p> <p>Queueing models</p> <p>Reinforcement learning algorithms</p>	Resource requirements from AlaaS	Computational resources	AlaaS
IM	Converts user intents to goals	<p>3GPP schema template.</p> <p>Python based goal generator</p>	User provided intents	User interface	
tSDG	Generates realistic and customizable datasets for AIoT model training of time-series data	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as PyTorch, pandas, NumPy, scikit.	Time series IoT datasets and domain expert knowledge in CSV format.	A realistic synthetic dataset consisting of time-series data across device, network, and	DAFL & DRFEC components

				app layers in CSV format.	
DACL	Phase 1 software component for imputing missing values and/or data labels, also doing rule-based data labeling.	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, Pandas, and NetworkX.	Training dataset in CSV format (tabular data, time-series)	An enhanced training dataset that has missing data and labels filled in	No
FRLM	This component aims to enable federated (representational) learning (FRL) within the PANDORA ecosystem. It consists of two main parts: the FRL server and the FRL Edge.	Python with libraries and frameworks such as pandas, NumPy, scikit-learn, Keras and flwr.	Datasets uploaded from edge devices and configuration inputs for the FL training component.	A global data representation model that can be exploited for outlier detection in unsupervised learning settings and for classification in supervised learning settings.	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism
ADOA	The component dynamically adjusts deep learning (DL) models to fit specific application requirements and resource constraints, optimizing factors like inference time, accuracy, resource usage, and energy consumption without retraining the model.	Python libraries, e.g., Pytorch	ONNX format for DL model description, graph or topology models for infrastructure specification	Optimized DL model solutions including splitting, pruning, quantization, or early-exit approaches.	CaaS,AlaaS
CRV	Phase 2 software component for continuous learning of AIoT predictive models	Python with the industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow,	Continuously delivered training tabular/time-series datasets structured as sequences of learning tasks	Predictive regression models	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism, AlaaS: AI model registry

		NumPy, pandas).			
DICE	The component focuses on providing explainability for AIoT systems after the inference phase.	Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.	Data (e.g., time series, data series); domain knowledge (e.g., rules, knowledge graphs, path plans, physics laws); learning models	Uncertainty quantification for predictions, and Physics Informed Neural Networks	tSDG, CRV, FRL, CIM, DEL, AlaaS: AI model registry, CaaS

3.1.3 Generic pipeline PCL

Table 18 provides details on the interaction between AlaaS, CaaS, and IM and the specific interactions of the other PANDORA core components within the use case of PCL and its roles of the different components. It also provides vital information on the components used tools, along with detailed information regarding the input and output date, by also highlighting any dependencies or changes within the component per use case.

Table 18: PCL Generic pipeline table

Component	Description and role	Tools	Input data/Models	Output data/Models	Dependencies
AlaaS	Manages the entire AI lifecycle and has the following sub-components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model registry • Model selector • Model lifecycle manager • Model inferencing • Model Re-training 	Model registry: MLFlow Model selection: Graph and meta-model search over MLflow Model lifecycle management: Meta-model-based drift detection	Trained models, time series data, synthetic data (Phase 1)	Selected, optimized, and deployed models for inference	CaaS (resources)
CaaS	Provides the necessary computational resources for training and inferencing. It acts as the resource	Benchmarking tools Queueing models	Resource requirements from AlaaS	Computational resources	AlaaS

	provider for the AlaaS.	Reinforcement learning algorithms			
IM	Converts user intents to goals	3GPP schema template. Python based goal generator	User provided intents	User interface	
vSDG	Generates synthetic datasets from limited real images to perform defect detection and classification.	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as PyTorch, pandas, NumPy, scikit.	Limited real images of products with defects	Synthetic dataset with defects; anomaly classification/detection	no
QU-MAD	Extract, quantify, and communicate the uncertainties from data and AI models in AIoT systems using Bayesian and Ensemble approaches. Additionally, it incorporates a user-feedback mechanism to annotate and adapt based on user trust, ultimately improving AI model performance and trustworthiness	Python 3.9 or more, ML frameworks and libraries (PyTorch, Lightning GDAL, Gradio, ...)	Raw data from AIoT system; synthetic generated data	Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback	SDG, DACL
CRV	Phase 2 software component for continuous learning of AIoT predictive models	Python with the industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow)	Images structured as a sequence of learning tasks	Supervised anomaly detection model for images	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism, AlaaS: AI model registry

3.1.4 Generic pipeline FRA

Table 19 below focus on the interaction between AlaaS, CaaS, and IM and the specific interactions of the other PANDORA core components within the use case of FRA and its roles of the different components. It also provides vital information on the components used tools, along with detailed information regarding the input and output date, by also highlighting any dependencies or changes withing the component per use case.

Table 19: FRA Generic pipeline table

Component	Description and role	Tools	Input data/Models	Output data/Models	Dependencies
AlaaS	<p>Manages the entire AI lifecycle and has the following sub-components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model registry • Model selector • Model lifecycle manager • Model inferencing • Model Re-training 	<p>Model registry: MLFlow</p> <p>Model selection: Graph and meta-model search over MLflow</p> <p>Model lifecycle management: Meta-model-based drift detection</p>	Trained models, time series data, synthetic data (Phase 1)	Selected, optimized, and deployed models for inference	CaaS(resource s)
CaaS	Provides the necessary computational resources for training and inferencing. It acts as the resource provider for the AlaaS.	<p>Benchmarking tools</p> <p>Queueing models</p> <p>Reinforcement learning algorithms</p>	Resource requirements from AlaaS	Computational resources	AlaaS
IM	Converts user intents to goals	<p>3GPP schema templates</p> <p>Python based goal generator</p>	User provided intents	User interface	
QU-MAD	aims to extract, quantify, and communicate the uncertainties from data and AI models in AIoT	Python 3.9 or more, ML frameworks and libraries (PyTorch, Lightning)	Raw data from AIoT system; synthetic generated data	Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties	SDG, DACL

	<p>systems using Bayesian and Ensemble approaches. Additionally, it incorporates a user-feedback mechanism to annotate and adapt based on user trust, ultimately improving AI model performance and trustworthiness</p>	<p>GDAL, Gradio, ...)</p>		<p>for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback</p>	
DEL	<p>Using the knowledge of AIoT experts, the module aims to develop explainable AI models, based on geometrical symmetries, to detect critical situations in the scenario. Moreover, causal feature subsets will be extracted from the data to serve for dimensionality reduction and performance optimization.</p>	<p>Python 3.9+, scientific computation libraries, ML libraires, Python libraires, TensorFlow</p>	<p>Time/Data series, domain knowledge (rules, knowledge graphs) and learning tasks.</p>	<p>Libraries of GENEOS and/or causal structures</p>	<p>SDG, DACL</p>
DACL	<p>Phase 1 software component for imputing missing values and/or data labels</p>	<p>Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, pandas, and NetworkX.</p>	<p>Training dataset in CSV format (tabular data, time-series)</p>	<p>An enhanced training dataset that has missing data and labels filled</p>	<p>No</p>

DRFE	Provides dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction while retaining the most essential data information	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, pandas, NumPy	Time series IoT datasets in CSV format.	Processed data with reduced dimensions and complexity, along with metrics quantifying the reduction and complexity. The metrics are optional. The output will be either .csv or json	No
CRV	Learning of time to event/failure prediction model	Python with the industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, pandas).	Time-series	Time-To-Event prediction or Survival Analysis trained model to be used for inference and for the explainability DICE component.	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism, AlaaS: AI model registry
DICE	The component focuses on providing explainability for AIoT systems after the inference phase.	Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.	Time-series; domain knowledge (e.g., maintenance interventions); learning model, test point and prediction to be explained	Explanations including feature subsets, or causal explanations (counterfactual explanations)	SDG, CRV, FRL, CIM, DEL

3.1.5 Generic pipeline HALCOR

Table 20 focuses on the interaction between AlaaS, CaaS, and IM and the specific interactions of the other PANDORA core components within the use case of HALCOR and its roles of the different components. It also provides vital information on the components used tools, along with detailed information regarding the input and output date, by also highlighting any dependencies or changes withing the components per use case.

Table 20: HALCOR Generic pipeline table

Component	Description and role	Tools	Input data/Models	Output data/Models	Dependencies
AlaaS	<p>Manages the entire AI lifecycle and has the following sub-components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model registry • Model selector • Model lifecycle manager • Model inferencing • Model Re-training 	<p>Model registry: MLFlow</p> <p>Model selection: Graph and meta-model search over MLflow</p> <p>Model lifecycle management: Meta-model-based drift detection</p>	Trained models, time series data, synthetic data (Phase 1)	Selected, optimized and deployed models for inference	CaaS (resources)
CaaS	Provides the necessary computational resources for training and inferencing. It acts as the resource provider for the AlaaS.	<p>Benchmarking tools</p> <p>Queueing models</p> <p>Reinforcement learning algorithms</p>	Resource requirements from AlaaS	Computational resources	AlaaS
IM	Converts user intents to goals	<p>3GPP schema template.</p> <p>Python based goal generator</p>	User provided intents	User interface	
tSDG	Generates realistic and customizable datasets for AIoT model training of time-series data	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as PyTorch, pandas, NumPy, scikit.	Time series IoT datasets and domain expert knowledge in CSV format.	A realistic synthetic dataset consisting of time-series data across device, network, and app layers in CSV format.	DACL & DRFEC components
QU-MAD	Aims to extract, quag AI model performance and trust worthiness	Python 3.9 or more, ML frameworks and libraries	Raw data from AIoT system; synthetic	Quantified uncertainties in data and models;	SDG and DACL

	notify, and communicate the uncertainties from data and AI models in AIoT systems using Bayesian and Ensemble approaches. Additionally, it incorporates a user-feedback mechanism to annotate and adapt based on user trust, ultimately improving	(PyTorch, Lightning GDAL, Gradio, ...)	generated data	Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback	
DEL	Develops domain-specific explainable AI models by leveraging geometrical symmetries and incorporating domain knowledge to enhance interpretability and causal explanations	ML libraries	Time/Data series, domain knowledge (rules, knowledge graphs, or time constraints), learning task	Libraries of GENEOS and/or causal structures	tSDG, DACL
DACL	Phase 1 software component for imputing missing values and/or data labels	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, Pandas, and NetworkX.	Training dataset in CSV format (tabular data, time-series)	An enhanced training dataset that has missing data and labels filled in	No
DRFE	Provides dimensionality reduction, feature extraction, and complexity reduction while retaining the most essential data information	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks such as scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, pandas, NumPy	Time series IoT datasets in CSV format.	An enhanced training dataset that has missing data and labels filled in	No

<p>CRV</p>	<p>Phase 2 software component for continuous learning of AIoT predictive models</p>	<p>Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.</p>	<p>Continuously delivered training tabular/time-series datasets structured as sequences of learning tasks</p>	<p>Predictive regression models</p>	<p>AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism, AlaaS: AI model registry</p>
<p>DICE</p>	<p>The component focuses on providing explainability for AIoT systems after the inference phase.</p>	<p>Python, along with libraries such as scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, and pandas for machine learning tasks.</p>	<p>Data (e.g., time series, data series); domain knowledge (e.g., rules, knowledge graphs, time constraints); model trained on optimal causal subspace given by DEL, test point and prediction to be explained tasks</p>	<p>Explanations in the form of causal feature subspaces</p>	<p>tSDG, CRV, FRL, CIM, DEL, AlaaS: AI model registry, CaaS</p>
<p>CIM</p>	<p>The component provides efficient, frame-by-frame classification or regression for sequence data, such as image sequences or time-series streams, enabling low-latency and high-throughput inference for AIoT systems.</p>	<p>Python with the industry standard libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing (scikit-learn, PyTorch, TensorFlow, NumPy, pandas).</p>	<p>Image sequence stream (images in PNG/Jpeg/Raw format); time series (sensor recording streams in binary format formed by data frames of duration 1, 0.5, 0.1, etc. seconds, depending on the use case requirements) ; network video stream (RTSP).</p>	<p>Classification or regression results in real-time with each frame or snippet of input data.</p>	<p>AlaaS</p>

3.2 Generic pipelines per component

The following tables (21-25) highlight the generic pipeline per component, where the pipeline is adapted to fit the use case:

- Component with its relative strategy
- Identified relative phase
- Used tools for corresponding component are identified
- The input and output data is recognized
- Detailed steps of how component was applied are defined
- Additional notes regards any changes or constraints are identified

3.2.1 Generic pipeline per component SAG

Each pipeline below is defined by the technical leader of the respective component. Use case-specific deviations are highlighted separately in Section 4. Information regarding the detailed steps of each component application is provided regarding SAG in Table 21 below.

Table 21: Generic pipeline Per component SAG table

Component (strategy)	Phase	Tools	Input → Output	Steps (detailed component leader)	Notes
QU-MAD	1	Python, ML frameworks libraries	Raw data from AIoT system; Synthetic generated data → Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback.	Methodology described in Deliverable D3.1	Implementation and training for Uncertainty Quantification in progress
tSDG	1	Python, ML libraries	Time series data → Realistic synthetic dataset	Described in Deliverable 3.1	
DEL	1	Python, scientific computation libraries, ML libraires, Python libraries	Time series data, Domain knowledge → Libraries of GENEOS	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Work in progress, we are perfecting and expanding the implementation of the GENEOS libraries

DRFE	1	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks	Structured time series IoT data → Processed data with reduced dimensions and complexity	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Experiments on newly provided dataset in progress
FRLM	2	Python, ML libraires	Dataset from edge devices → Global data representation model	Described in Deliverable 4.1	
ADOA	2	Python libraires	ONNX format for DL model → Optimized DL model solutions	Described in Deliverable 4.1	
CRV	2	Python	Continuous training data → Continuously updated predictive models	Described in Deliverable 4.1	
DICE	2	Python, TensorFlow, Machine learning libraries and frameworks	Time/Data series, Domain knowledge, Learning tasks → Libraries of GENEOS, or sets of causal features	Described in Deliverable 4.1	
CIM	2	Python libraires	Time series data → Prediction of future network outage, either as a label (classification) or a possibility (regression)	Described in Deliverable 4.1	

3.2.1.1 Pipelines mapping to UC scenarios

Each component should be described according to the following structure.

tSDG

- **S1:** tSDG leverages Causal Discovery to extract relationships from the dataset, resulting in causal graphs that will then be used by a GAN/Diffusion model to generate realistic synthetic time-series

QU-MAD

- **S1:** QU-MAD helps to minimize and prevent potential type I and type II errors (false positives and false negatives) with uncertainty quantification

DEL

- **S1, S2:** Taking as input a set of time series of an AIoT infrastructure, develops explainable models based on GENEOS or causal structures to detect critical situations in the scenario (i.e., network bandwidth saturation)

DRFEC

- **S1, S2:** DRFEC will be used in both scenarios to retain the most informative aspects of the given data while discarding noise and redundancy.

CRV

- **S1, S2:** In both scenarios CRV continuously trains regression models predicting different target variables (transmitted throughput, packet count)

DICE

- **S1, S2:** Library of GENEOS adapted to work in the continual learning setting

CIM

- **S1, S2:** CIM predicts if an error is going to happen in the near future efficiently

3.2.2 Generic pipeline per component EAB

Each pipeline below is defined by the technical leader of the respective component. Use case-specific deviations are highlighted separately in Section 4. Information regarding the detailed steps of the components application are provided regarding EAB in Table 22 below.

Table 22: Generic pipeline Per component EAB table

Component (strategy)	Phase	Tools	Input → Output	Steps (detailed component leader)	Notes
DACL	1	MLFlow, python libraries	Training dataset in CSV format → enhanced training dataset without missing values and with rule-based anomaly labels	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Dependencies Raw data from InfluxDB, output to tSDG, DEL, QU-MAD
tSDG	1	Python, ML libraries	Time series data in CSV format → Synthetic time-series data	Described in Deliverable 3.1	
FRLM	2	Python, ML libraries	Dataset from edge devices → Global data representation model	Described in Deliverable 4.1	
ADOA	2	Python, ML libraries	ONNX format for DL model → optimized DL model solutions	Described in Deliverable 4.1	
CRV	2	Python	Continuous training data → continuously updated predictive model	Described in Deliverable 4.1	
DICE	2	Python, TensorFlow, Machine	Time series data; Domain knowledge; Point/prediction to	Described in D4.1	

		learning libraries and frameworks	explain → Uncertainty quantification of prediction or Physics-informed explanations		
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3.2.2.1 Pipelines mapping to UC scenarios

tSDG

- **S1, S2:** tSDG leverages Causal Discovery to extract relationships from the dataset, resulting in causal graphs that will then be used by a GAN/Diffusion model to generate realistic synthetic time-series

●

DAKL

- **S1, S2:** DAKL imputes missing values and annotates data points with anomaly labels according to given knowledge-based rules

FRLM

- **S1, S2:** Federated learning of compact data representations for training unsupervised and supervised anomaly detection models

ADOA

- **S1:** ADOA is being integrated in the MVP of UC2S1 and is able to communicate with AlaaS to retrieve a model and by using profiling find the host that will run it faster and perform deployment in Kubernetes

CRV

- **S2:** CRV continuously trains AIoT predictive models predicting latency and throughput for intent driven networking purposes.

3.2.3 Generic pipeline per component PCL

Each pipeline below is defined by the technical leader of the respective component. Use case-specific deviations are highlighted separately in Section 4. Information regarding the detailed steps of the components application are provided regarding PCL in Table 23 below.

Table 23: Generic pipeline Per component PCL table

Component (strategy)	Phase	Tools	Input → Output	Steps (detailed component leader)	Notes
vSDG (1)	1	Python, ML libraries	Limited dataset of real defect images → Rich synthetic dataset, anomaly detection & classification	Described in D3.1	Exploitation of new dataset in progress

QU-MAD (2)	1	Python, ML frameworks libraries	Raw data from AIoT system; Synthetic generated data → Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback.	Described in D3.1	experiments models for new PCL data in progress
CRV (7)	2	Python	Continuous training data (images) → Continuously updated supervised anomaly detection model	The initial anomaly detection model is formed considering normal images and existing anomalous images. The model is incrementally updated on novel anomaly classes.	The model type and architecture will be determined by WP3 tasks (T3.1 & T3.2)

3.2.3.1 Pipelines mapping to UC scenarios

vSDG

- **S1, S2:** vSDG generates realistic synthetic defect data to perform anomaly detection and classification.

QU-MAD

- **S1, S2:** QU-MAD provides uncertainty estimations to help for uncertainty reduction of defect predictions

CRV

- **S1, S2:** CRV continuously trains supervised anomaly detection models for images to identify defective products.

3.2.4 Generic pipeline per component FRA

Each pipeline below is defined by the technical leader of the respective component. Use case-specific deviations are highlighted separately in Section 4. Information regarding the detailed steps of each component application is provided with regards to FRA in Table 24 below.

Table 24: Generic pipeline Per component FRA table

Strategy	Phase	Tools	Input → Output	Steps (detailed component leader)	Notes
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DACL	1	Python, ML libraires	Raw CSV from InfluxDB Manual labels for known failure cases (sensor type, location, normal ranges) → Enhanced dataset with Missing sensor values imputed Anomaly labels	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Dependencies: structured data from InfluxDB, output to tSDG, DEL, QU-MAD
DEL	1	Python, scientific computation libraries, ML libraires, Python libraries	Time series data, Domain knowledge → Libraries of GENEOS, or sets of causal features	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Dependencies: DACL labeled data, Domain knowledge data, output to DICE. Tools developed, we are working on the experiments on the dataset
QU-MAD	1	Python, ML frameworks libraires	Raw data from AIoT system; synthetic generated data → Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback.	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Dependencies: tSDG synthetic data, DACL labeled data and output to CRV
CRV	2	Python	Time series → Time to event/failure prediction model	Described in Deliverable 4.1	Dependencies! AlaaS (model selection, registry), CaaS, output can be used for DICE
DRFE	1	Python, machine learning libraries and frameworks	Structured, time series IoT data → Processed data with reduced dimensions and complexity	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Experiments on newly provided dataset in progress
DICE	2	Python, TensorFlow	Anomaly prediction (including model, training data, test point) → Explanation	Described in Deliverable 4.1	Dependencies: AlaaS (model selection,

					registry), CaaS, DEL, CRV
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3.2.4.1 Pipelines mapping to UC scenarios

DAKL

- **S1:** DAKL imputes missing values and missing labels (including anomaly labels). Anomaly annotations can be also imputed by given knowledge-based rules.

DEL

- **S1, S2:** DEL provides the "why" behind anomalies by connecting data patterns to physical processes (e.g., "Pressure spike caused by compressor overspeed due to cooling system failure"). Taking as input a set of time series of an AIoT infrastructure, develops explainable models based on GENEOS or causal structures to detect critical situations in the scenario

QU-MAD

- **S1:** QU-MAD helps reduce false positives by providing confidence scores for anomaly predictions
- **S2:** Uncertainty feedback guides retraining (focus on high-uncertainty cases)

CRV

- **S1, S2:** CRV (re-)trains time to event/failure prediction models

DICE

- **S1, S2:** Provide time-sensitive explanations for time to event predictions in the form of counterfactual explanations, i.e., time-specific feature updates that can postpone the event.

DRFEC

- **S1:** DRFEC will be used to retain the most informative aspects of the given data while discarding noise and redundancy.

3.2.5 Generic pipeline per component HALCOR

Each pipeline below is defined by the technical leader of the respective component. Use case-specific deviations are highlighted separately in Section 4. Information regarding the detailed steps of each component application is provided with regards to HALCOR in Table 25 below.

Table 25: Generic pipeline Per component HALCOR table

Component (strategy)	Phase	Tools	Input→ Output	Steps (detailed component leader)	Notes
tSDG	1	MLFlow, Python libraries	Time-series data in CSV format → Synthetic time-series data	Described in Deliverable 3.1	

QU-MAD	1	Python, ML frameworks libraries	Raw data from AIoT system; Synthetic generated data → Quantified uncertainties in data and models; Visualizations of uncertainties for end-users; Adapted AI models based on user feedback.	Described in Deliverable 3.1 for uncertainty quantification	Tool implemented for visualizations of uncertainties
DEL	1	ML libraires	Time series data; Domain knowledge; Learning tasks → Libraries of GENEOS, or sets of causal features	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Dependencies: DACL labeled data, domain knowledge data, output to DICE
DACL	1	Python, ML libraries	Training dataset in CSV format → Enhanced training dataset without missing values	Described in Deliverable 3.1	
DRFE	1	Python, ML libraries and frameworks	Structured time series IoT data → Processed data with reduced dimensions and complexity	Described in Deliverable 3.1	Testing new DRFEC methods in progress
CRV	2	Python, ML libraries	Continuous training data → Continuously updated predictive models	Described in Deliverable 4.1	AlaaS Data Collection Mechanism, AlaaS: AI model registry
DICE	2	Python, TensorFlow	Time series data tested on model built on reduced subspace by DEL → Global explanation being the reduced causal feature subspace	Described in Deliverable 4.1	Dependencies AlaaS (model selection, registry), CaaS, DEL, CRV
CIM	2	Python libraries	Time series data → Prediction of energyconsumption in the future (regression)	Described in Deliverable 4.1	

3.2.5.1 Pipelines mapping to UC scenarios

Each component should be described according to the following structure.

tSDG

- **S1:** tSDG leverages Causal Discovery to extract relationships from the raw dataset, resulting in causal graphs that are then used by a diffusion-based model (i.e., Diffusion-TS) to generate realistic synthetic time-series

QU-MAD

- **S1:** QU-MAD helps to assess the confidence in the energy consumption forecasts

DEL

- **S1, S2:** DEL provides the "why" behind energy forecasting values in different horizons, by finding equivalent multivariate subspaces of the time series that can optimally predict the target. Thus, the returned subspaces can be used not only to explain but also to optimize the forecasting task, in predictive performance and efficiency

DACL

- **S1, S2:** DACL imputes missing values in training datasets

DRFEC

- **S1, S2:** DRFEC will be used in both scenarios to retain the most informative aspects of the given data while discarding noise and redundancy.

CRV

- **S1:** CRV continuously trains regression models predicting energy consumption

DICE

- **S1, S2:** DICE uses the output feature subspace of DEL to globally explain the predictions of the forecasting model built on the same feature subspace.

CIM

- **S1, S2:** CIM predicts the expected consumption at every time step efficiently.

4 Pipeline adaptation per scenario

4.1 Blueprints overview

4.1.1 SAG

Below, the decomposed sequence diagrams for the SAG sequence diagrams of their scenarios. More detailed sequence diagrams of each scenario and each phase can be found in D2.2.

The sequence diagram in Figure 2 illustrates the process of dynamically optimizing system performance in response to high delay and resource demand using PANDORA. In Phase 1, training data is prepared to include both “normal” and “anomalous” data points that capture potential infrastructure failures. During run-time operation (Phase 2), the data can be retrieved from Phase 1 generated datasets and fed into "Phase 2 components" for continuous learning. The AlaaS component automatically selects appropriate continuous learning and explanation models, which are trained in a federated environment to enhance privacy. Inference results from continuous learning are sent to scenario deployment domain to trigger necessary actuations such as adjustments in resource allocation. Finally, explanations are provided to the actor to enhance trust in the AIoT system’s decision-making.

Figure 2: Sequence Diagram of SAG Scenarios

4.1.2 EAB

Below, the decomposed sequence diagrams for the EAB sequence diagrams of their scenarios, more detailed sequence diagrams of each scenario, and each phase can be found in D2.2.

Figure 3 illustrates the process of safe robot planning with communication quality awareness using PANDORA. Domain knowledge and sensory data about the environment of the robot are collected and used for synthetic data generation and augmentation using tSDG in Phase 1. During the run-time phase, the actor must be authenticated to interact with the framework via UA and IM, where they can specify requirements and receive inference results. IM interprets the user's requirements and communicates with the AlaaS platform for inferencing. AlaaS, in turn, requests computational resources using CaaS to enable continuous learning and generate explanations. The Continuous Learning (CRV) component considers the robot's current status and the user's communication quality requirements to produce a safe planning strategy for the robot as well as configurations to the 5G network controller.

Figure 3: Sequence Diagram of EAB Scenarios

4.1.3 PCL

Below, the decomposed sequence diagrams of each scenario and phase should be included with explaining, it could be found in D2.2.

As shown in Figure 4, in PCL’s scenarios, Phase 1 involves generating synthetic data using vSDG based on real images datasets, CAD drawings or 3D models provided by the actors. Synthetic data is specifically created to represent potential defects that are available in limited instances in real datasets. Explanations are essential to offer the actor insights into the accuracy of the synthetic images and their annotations. Continues Learning is used in the run-time phase to generate visual inspection AI model for anomaly detection.

Figure 4: Sequence Diagram of PCL Scenarios

4.1.4 FRA

As shown in Figure 5 In the FRA Scenario, anomalies would be detected at early stages to predict potential risks like component shutdowns, extreme high pressure, or temperature out of range to increase safety and availability of the hydrogen refueling station. The data from the station is used to train AI models for predictive maintenance and operational safety. By integrating AI-based

analytics, the system identifies hazardous states and predicts equipment failures, ensuring safe and efficient refueling operations while minimizing costs.

Figure 5: Sequence Diagram of FRA Scenarios

4.1.5 HALCOR

Below, the decomposed sequence diagrams of each scenario and phase should be included with explaining, it could be found in D2.2.

Figure 6 shows HALCOR’s scenarios that leverage the PANDORA framework for predicting the next hour’s energy consumption of the extrusion. Initially, the scenario domain provides real-time observations, past consumption patterns, and/or planned production schedules to Phase 1 components for augmented synthetic data generation to enrich and enhance the input data. In Phase 2, it mainly involves energy consumption prediction and result display by web-based GUI (part of the PANDORA IM).

Figure 6: Sequence Diagram of HALCOR Scenarios

5 Scenario specific pipeline Adaptations Changes

This section documents the current implementation status and any deviations from the originally planned pipeline instantiation for each use case scenario per component. As PANDORA components transition from development (documented in WP3 and WP4 deliverables) to deployment within specific industrial contexts, various factors necessitate adaptations and time frames: dataset availability and quality, component maturity, technical constraints, and evolving use case requirements.

For each of the five industrial pilots (SAG, EAB, PCL, FRA, and HALCOR)(Table 26-30) and their respective scenarios, this section provides systematic tracking of:

- **Component application status:** Whether each PANDORA component (tSDG/vSDG, QU-MAD, DEL, DAQL, DRFE, FRLM, ADOA, CRV, DICE, CIM) has been successfully applied to the use case dataset (O = Applied) or remains in progress (X = Not yet applied)
- **Implementation changes:** Modifications to the planned component integration approach, including methodological adjustments, workflow alterations, or technical workarounds necessitated by pilot-specific conditions
- **Rationale:** Explanations for deviations from the original plan, including dataset-related challenges (delayed availability, data quality issues, target label clarification), component dependencies (requiring outputs from WP3 methods before proceeding), technical prerequisites (testbed extensions, model retraining), or coordination issues between work packages.

This tracking mechanism serves multiple purposes: it provides transparency regarding implementation progress for project management and external reviewers, it documents lessons learned that inform similar industrial AI deployments beyond PANDORA, it identifies systematic challenges (such as dataset availability) that affect multiple components and pilots and it establishes a baseline for evaluating progress in subsequent reporting periods.

The tables in subsections 5.1 through 5.5 should be completed collaboratively by strategy providers (technical partners from WP3 and WP4 responsible for component development) and use case partners (industrial pilots responsible for providing datasets and operational context).

This collaborative documentation ensures that both technical and operational perspectives are represented in understanding implementation challenges and solutions.

As component implementations mature and pilot datasets stabilize during the next reporting period, many components currently marked as "not yet applied" (X) are expected to transition to "applied" (O), with corresponding updates to the "Changes" and "Reason" columns reflecting successful integration or any remaining adaptation requirements.

5.1 SAG

Table 26 below describes and helps keep track the state of implementation and execution of the different component for the SAG use case scenario, it can help provide information of any changes, constraints or difficulties happening in regards of implementing the components per scenario. If any changes occur from the original scenario to this point, please note them below, and the table should be filled in by strategy providers and technical partners.

Table 26: SAG Scenario specific adaptation table

Use case	Applied to UC dataset: yes (x)/Not yet (O)	Changes	Reason
UC1S1(SAG)	tSDG (O)	Still in progress, we are still processing the dataset with Causal Discovery algorithms before we generate new synthetic time-series	We are in the process of trying to yield "better" results with Causal Discovery algorithms in order to produce more meaningful causal graphs, before we continue with the Diffusion-TS, train and generate new synthetic time-series. As soon as this gets settled, we will produce the synthetic time-series.
	QU-MAD (X)	Work in progress, we are still implementing and training our probabilistic methods for quantifying uncertainties on new dataset	New dataset provided with delay
	DEL (X)	Work in progress, we are perfecting and expanding the implementation of the GENEOS libraries	Delayed availability of the data and late confirmation of the target labels.
	DRFE (O)	Ongoing experimentation with DRFEC methods due to newly provided data and updated target labels	Delayed availability of the data and late confirmation of the target labels.
	CRV (X)	Experimental work on new dataset not started	New dataset provided with delay, it is not yet finalized by WP3 methods (removal of irrelevant & constant features)
	FRLM (X)	Work in progress, the testbed implementation needs to be extended to multiple simulated production cells, so that federation concept can be applied.	As an initial step, non-federated dataset was delivered to test the models through central training.
	DICE (X/O)	Work in progress, we are perfecting and expanding the implementation of the GENEOS libraries	Delayed availability of the data and late confirmation of the target labels.
	CIM (X)	Work in progress, we have analyzed the feasibility of Continual Transformers for SAG	New datasets were delivered after the feedback.

		Use case and provided feedback about the SAG datasets	
	ADOA (X)	Work in progress	We need to retrain the Profiler based on the model that these use case will use
UC1S2(SAG)	tSDG (O)	Still in progress, we are still processing the dataset with Causal Discovery algorithms before we generate new synthetic time-series	We are in the process of trying to yield better results with Causal Discovery algorithms in order to produce better causal graphs, before we continue with the Diffusion-TS, train and generate new synthetic time-series. As soon as this gets settled, we will produce the synthetic time-series.
	DRFE (X)	Ongoing experimentation with DRFEC methods due to newly provided data and updated target labels	Delayed availability of the data and late confirmation of the target labels.
	CRV (X)	Experimental work on new dataset not started	New dataset provided with delay, it is not yet finalized by WP3 methods (removal of irrelevant & constant features)
	FRLM (X)	Work in progress, the testbed implementation needs to be extended to multiple simulated production cells, so that federation concept can be applied.	As an initial step, non-federated dataset was delivered to test the models through central training.
	CIM (X)	Work in progress, we have analyzed the feasibility of Continual Transformers for SAG Use case and provided feedback about the SAG datasets	New datasets were delivered after the feedback.
	ADOA (X)	Work in progress	We need to retrain the Profiler based on the model that these use case will use

5.2 EAB

Table 27 describes and helps keep track the state of implementation and execution of the different component for the EAB use case scenario, it can help provide information of any changes, constraints or difficulties happening in regards of implementing the components per scenario. If any changes occur from the original scenario to this point, please note them below, and the table should be filled in by strategy providers and technical partners.

Table 27: EAB Scenario specific adaptation table

Use case	Applied to UC dataset: yes (x)/Not yet (O)	Changes	Reason
UC2S1(EAB)	tSDG (O)	Different approach in handling the EAB dataset for generating time-series, due to irregularity.	As the dataset is irregular (not consecutive time intervals), we need to explore different GAN/Diffusion based models that can incorporate an irregular dataset. The model that we are using for the other use cases, expects only regular time-series datasets as input.
	DACL (O)	No changes; Missing values and rule-based anomaly labels successfully imputed, resulting data used by FRLM for federated representational learning and unsupervised anomaly detection model construction	
	FRLM (O)	No changes; Federated representational learning model for unsupervised anomaly detection integrated in MVP/test bed, model validation described in Deliverable 4.1	
	ADOA (O)	The profiler component of ADOA had to be retrained	This happened since the faded model used in PANDORA used different type of layers from the ones that profiler was able to identify in its previous version.
UC2S2(EAB)	tSDG(X)	Different approach in handling the EAB dataset for generating time-series, due to irregularity.	As the dataset is irregular (not consecutive time intervals), we need to explore different GAN/Diffusion based models that can incorporate an irregular dataset. The model that we are using for the other use cases, expects only regular time-series datasets as input.

	DACL (O)	No changes; Missing values and rule-based anomaly labels successfully imputed, resulting data used for continuous learning experiments in Task 4.1 (CRV)	
	ADOA (X)	Work in progress	We need to retrain the Profiler based on the model that these use case will use
	CRV (O)	Work in progress; MAML-based continual learning solution does not show satisfactory performance due to synthetic divisions of dataset into learning tasks for meta-model training	Pilot data do not correspond to a sequence of learning tasks (it is time-series that can be provisory divided into learning tasks). MAML meta-model training on synthetically generated learning tasks (by methods from 3.1) should be explored, as well as alternative solutions based on continual fine-tuning of foundation models
	DICE (O)	Work in progress	

5.3 PCL

Table 28 describes and helps keep track the state of implementation and execution of the different component for the PCL use case scenario, it can help provide information of any changes, constraints or difficulties happening in regards of implementing the components per scenario. If any changes occur from the original scenario to this point, please note them below, and the table should be filled by strategy providers, and technical partners.

Table 28: PCL Scenario specific adaptation table

Use case	Applied to UC dataset: yes (x)/Not yet (O)	Changes	Reason
UC3S1(PCL)	vSDG (x)	Need to run with the new dataset from PCL that has been restructured, introduced new defect categories and enriched number of samples; validate results	The dataset so far had 49 samples and 6 defect categories; The new dataset has 158 samples, 4 categories and also provides 60 good samples
	QU-MAD (X)	Need to apply uncertainty quantification methodologies on new dataset	Dataset provided with delay and re-adapt method to generate uncertainty maps as well

	CRV (X)	Need to develop continual learning methods for images (CRV currently supports tabular data)	The best NN-based model (model type & architecture) for anomaly detection on PCL images should be identified in WP3, CRV will provide continuous learning updates of that model
UC3S2(PCL)	vSDG (O)	Need to run with the new dataset from PCL that has been restructured, introduced new defect categories and enriched number of samples; validate results	The dataset so far had 49 samples and 6 defect categories; the new dataset has 158 samples, 4 categories and also provides 60 good samples
	QU-MAD (X)	Need to develop uncertainty quantification methods on 3d files	Need to experiment different probabilistic models with this type of data
	CRV (X)	Need to develop continual learning methods for images (CRV currently supports tabular data)	The best NN-based model (model type & architecture) for anomaly detection on PCL images should be identified in WP3, CRV will provide continuous learning updates of that model

5.4 FRA

Table 29 describes and helps keep track the state of implementation and execution of the different component for the FRA use case scenario, it can help provide information of any changes, constraints or difficulties happening in regards of implementing the components per scenario. If any changes occur from the original scenario to this point, please note them below, and the table should be filled by strategy providers, and technical partners.

Table 29: FRA Scenario specific adaptation table

Use case	Applied to UC dataset: yes (x)/Not yet (O)	Changes	Reason
UC4S1(FRA)	QU-MAD (X)	Work in progress, we are still experimenting since different versions of datasets were provided	A majority of the first dataset contained missing values. Consequently, a second dataset was provided later. We still need to process this dataset as the target are not similar to the first dataset.

	DEL (O)	Work in progress.	Delayed availability of the data and late confirmation of the target labels. We now transform the data into a forecasting problem (RUL prediction) to test the Chronoepilogi solution developed in the DEL component.
	DACL (X)	Work in progress on the second dataset	Extremely large fraction of missing values in the first dataset making DACL highly inaccurate for any further application
	DRFE (X)	Ongoing experimentation with DRFEC methods due to newly provided data and not finalized target labels	Delayed availability of the data and still no confirmation of the target labels.
	CRV (O)	CRV includes now the Time-To-Event prediction model construction	We need an initial model to create the predictions to be explained for the DICE component. For the moment, we have had to design the prediction problems as the target was not unique. We are experimenting with Survival Analysis and Remaining Useful Life predictive algorithms. However, the data has been updated, and new data preprocessing and experiments have to be done.
	DICE (X)	Work in progress.	We need a well-performing prediction model from CRV component in order to design meaningful explanations. For the moment, we are investigating black-box explanations, with experiments being

			made on open data sets.
UC4S2(FRA)	QU-MAD (X)	Need to experiment on quantifying uncertainties with new dataset first	Need outputs from scenario 1 with new dataset, process the data and need to confirm target values
	CRV (X)	No changes; dataset for Scenario 2 not available to retrain Time-To-Event prediction model	

5.5 HALCOR

Table 30 describes and helps keep track the state of implementation and execution of the different component for the HALCOR use case scenario, it can help provide information of any changes, constraints or difficulties happening in regards of implementing the components per scenario. If any changes occur from the original scenario to this point, please note them below, and the table should be filled by strategy providers, and technical partners.

Table 30: HALCOR Scenario specific adaptation table

Use case	Applied to UC dataset: yes (x)/Not yet (O)	Changes	Reason
UC5S1 (HALCOR)	tSDG (O)	No changes	Data model constraint
	QU-MAD (O)	No changes	
	DEL (O)	Our innovative Chronoepilogi algorithm (https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3737916.3742183) has been successfully applied on the use case data. Optimal causal feature subspaces have been found, serving as explanations and used also for dimensionality reduction. KPI2.4.1 has been addressed.	
	DAACL (O)	No changes; current HALCOR dataset does not have missing values and labels, the dataset was used to validate	

		NNTL-MVI data imputation method (work done in Oct and Nov 2025)	
	DRFE (O)	No changes	
	DICE (O)	Work in progress, changed continuous learning approach to continual fine-tuning of TabPFN foundation model, satisfactory experimental results (work done in Oct and Nov 2025)	
	CRV (O)	When the model is trained on the feature subspace given by the DEL component, then the features can serve as the explanations (most important and causal features).	Relatively small training dataset that cannot be divided into learning tasks for MAML meta-model training
	CIM (X)	Work in progress, we made preliminary tests with baselines and applied preprocessing on the datasets	We want to have a high-performing Continual model that achieves the corresponding KPI
UC5S2 (HALCOR)	DACL (O)	No changes; current HALCOR dataset does not have missing values and labels, the dataset was used to validate NNTL-MVI data imputation method (work done in Oct and Nov 2025)	
	DRFE (O)	No changes	
	CIM (X)	Work in progress, we made preliminary tests with baselines and applied preprocessing on the datasets	We want to have a high-performing Continual model that achieves the corresponding KPI

6 Validation Plan

Task 6.3 established a verification and validation framework that allows the systematic KPI mapping that links performance metrics to PANDORA strategies, components, and use case scenarios. This framework defines verification and validation variables (both independent and dependent) that enables objective assessment of PANDORA's performance for Phase 1 and Phase 2 technologies.

The following tables (31-40) present the current state of this analysis mapping each PANDORA component to its

- Strategy to which component belongs to
- GA Task which contributes to the development of the component
- enabler towards which the component contributes to
- KR to which the component leads at
- KPIs which the component contributes towards their achievement
- Verification variable that the project uses to measure success towards the KPIs
- Relevant metric and baseline value to compare against
- Expected and actual results that have been achieved so far towards the achievement of the KPI
- Follow-up actions
- Relevant UC scenarios

Table 31: Synthetic data generation (Strategy 1) – verification of tSDG and vSDG components

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Synthetic data generation (Strategy 1) T3.1	Synthetic data generation for time-series data tSDG [IMT/NTUA]	EN2.2: Models, mechanisms, and tools for data preparation and enrichment through the generation of synthetic data	KR2.1: Definition of ML-based semantic models for smart spaces via event-driven generation of synthetic datasets	KPI2.2.1	Increase model performance	Performance metrics tSDG: Compare the model performance without synthetic data vs. augmented with synthetic data vSDG: Train classifier with a minimum amount of real data and compare the performance of the model trained with additional synthetic data	tSDG: MAE, RMSE vSDG: f1 score (classification), IC-LPIPS, KID (defect quality)	Scores with the model trained with a minimum amount of real data	>=20% accuracy improvement over the baseline	on going development & testing	tSDG: Implement and evaluate the performance of the models of UC2 and UC5 vSDG: Generate defect images for the remaining defect categories, additional real images for training and evaluation, evaluation of classification results.	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 EAB: UC2S1, UC2S2 PCL: UC3S1, UC3S2 HALCOR: UC5S1
	Synthetic data generation for vision data vSDG [NTUA]			KPI2.2.3	Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data	Testing Against Baselines tSDG: Percentage of less data samples needed vSDG: Percentage of less real images needed	Percentage difference	0	>=15% less real images needed	on going development & testing	tSDG: Implement and evaluate the performance of the model of UC2 and UC5. vSDG: Generate defect images for the remaining defect categories, classification results.	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 EAB: UC2S1, UC2S2 PCL: UC3S1, UC3S2 HALCOR: UC5S1

Table 32: Uncertainty quantification (Strategy 2) – verification of QU-MAD component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Uncertainty quantification (Strategy 2) T3.2	Uncertainty quantification modelling and development QU-MAD [DLR]	EN1.2: Models, mechanisms, and tools for uncertainty modelling and quantification	KR1.2: Enhanced analysis, interpretation and understandability of data insights and optimised development and training of efficient and compact All models for domain-driven IoT data management and use	KPI1.2.1	Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction	Performance metrics/ metrics analysis Calibration	MSE, CRPS, Brier score/ECE, NLL	0	>=15% accuracy improvement in results	36% improvement for MSE; 21% improvement for CRPS on UC5S1 (Halcor)	Continuing experiments of UQ methods on PANDORA datasets and integrate human-in-the-loop system	SAG: UC1S1 PCL: UC3S1, UC3S2 FRA: UC4S1, UC4S2 HALCOR: UC5S1
				KPI1.2.2	Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem	Prototyping	Number of developed tools	1	>=1 tool	on going development & testing	Implementation of tool on UC5S1, and maybe other energy efficiency problem	SAG: UC1S1 PCL: UC3S1, UC3S2 HALCOR: UC5S1

Table 33: Explainable Domain-Informed modeling (Strategy 3) – verification of DEL component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
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Explainable Domain-informed modeling (Strategy 3) T3.3	Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning DEL [UNIFI]	EN2.1: Models, mechanisms, and techniques for semantic and causal data model formulation of smart spaces	KR2.1: Definition of ML-based semantic models for smart spaces via event-driven generation of synthetic datasets	KPI2.1.1	Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces	Pilot Studies Model inspection after a critical situation happens, necessary to understand what went wrong, why, and how to improve/retrain the model	Number of critical situations	100% critical situations	<=80% critical situations	on going development &testing	N/A	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 FRA: UC4S1, UC4S2
		EN2.1: Models, mechanisms, and techniques for semantic and causal data model formulation of smart spaces	KR2.1: Definition of ML-based semantic models for smart spaces via event-driven generation of synthetic datasets	KPI2.1.2	Number of models defined per smart space	Prototyping	Number of developed tools	2	>=2	on going development &testing	N/A	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 FRA: UC4S1, UC4S2
		EN2.4: A tool-based explainable AI and interpretation modelling framework for domain knowledge	KR2.2: Analysis of existing domain knowledge, and experimental datasets, simulation models and tools	KPI2.4.1	Number of improved properties characterising the quality of the provided explanations of continuous and domain-informed AI decisions >= 2	Performance metrics analysis Number of explanation properties improved.	Metric corresponding to each property.	0	>=2 improved properties	Chronoepiligi on the Halcor dataset has been tested successfully on three explainability properties: conciseness, fidelity and stability. Chronoepiligi has reduced the subset of features from 144 to 18, while improving or maintaining the forecasting performance. On different horizons, the predictive performance is also maintained for short predictive periods, and is improved in larger predictive windows	N/A	SAG: UC1S1 EAB: UC2S2 FRA: UC4S1, UC4S2 HALCOR: UC5S1

Table 34: Semi-automated annotations (Strategy 4) – verification of DACL component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC	
Semi-automated annotations (Strategy 4) T3.4	Semi-automated annotations, labelling and self-supervised completion and augmentation DACL [UNSPMF]	EN1.3: Models, mechanisms, and tools for (semi-) automated annotations and labelling	KR1.3: Novel data preparation, completion, and dimensionality reduction for optimised data provision and consumption processes towards more efficient, accurate and robust AI models	KPI1.3.1	Increase labelling and annotation accuracy	Performance metrics analysis comparison to baseline methods	Decrease in MAE and increase in R2 (coefficient of determination) for data imputation (missing value inference) models w.r.t. baseline models	0,2	0,2	MAE decrease in range [41.96%, 51.8%] on SIE dataset (UC1)	Further experimental evaluation of novel data imputation methods on PANDORA related datasets	EAB: UC2S1, UC2S2	
				KPI1.3.2	The number of predictive models achieving better performance after labelling and annotation >=3	Performance metrics analysis comparison to baseline methods	The number of models with positive decrease.	3	>=3	=13 on SIE dataset.	Further experimental evaluation of predictive models trained after novel data imputation methods on PANDORA related datasets	EAB: UC2S1 FRA: UC4S1	
		EN1.3: Models, mechanisms, and tools for (semi-) automated annotations and labelling	KR1.2: Enhanced analysis, interpretation and understandability of data insights and optimised development and training of efficient and compact AI models for domain-driven IoT data management and use	KPI1.3.3	Reduce human interventions	Pilot Studies	The number of human interventions.	The number of human interventions	check the datasets for all missing entries	0,5	100% - Novel MVI methods do not require human interventions	N/A	EAB: UC2S1
				KPI1.4.1	Decrease periodic human inspections on models	Pilot Studies	The number of human inspections on models	The number of human inspections on models	number of models check	0,2	If we assume that human inspection on data imputation models is required when the margin or error is high than 5% (R2 smaller than 0.95) then this kind of inspection in the case of SIE dataset is required for 8 out of 26 features when using novel PANDORA methods. This corresponds to decrease of approximately 70%.	Further experimental evaluation of predictive models trained after novel data imputation methods on PANDORA related datasets	EAB: UC2S1
		EN1.4: Models, mechanisms, and tools for self-supervision data completion and augmentation	KR1.2: Enhanced analysis, interpretation and understandability of data insights and optimised development and training of efficient and compact AI models for domain-driven IoT data management and use	KPI1.4.2	Numbers of models trained	Pilot Studies	The number of models having better predictive performance	The number of models having better predictive performance	Zero (0)	>=5	Five models for missing value imputation were trained on Siemens dataset: - SIMPLE – simple imputer from the scikit-learn library	Evaluation on other HALCOR PANDORA datasets	EAB: UC2S1

Table 35: Semi-automated annotations (Strategy 5) – verification of DRFEC component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Data summarisation (Strategy 5) T3.5	Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction Component DRFEC [ITML]	EN1.5: Models, mechanisms, and tools for data summarisation and dimensionality reduction	KR1.3: Novel data preparation, completion, and dimensionality reduction for optimised data provision and consumption processes towards more efficient, accurate and robust AI models	KPI1.5.1	Number of models trained	Pilot Studies	Number of models trained and tested using various dimensionality reduction methods across the experiments.	1	≥3	FRA: 5 HALCOR: 5	The DRFEC methods will be tested with new Machine Learning models on top. We will extend this evaluation to the SIEMENS use case as well by applying all the DRFEC methods tested on the previous datasets. We will further extend DRFEC with novel representational learning techniques.	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 FRA: UC4S1 HALCOR: UC5S1, UC5S2
				KPI1.5.2	Dimensionality reduction	Performance metrics analysis	Dimensionality reduction rates of complexity without sacrificing model performance	0	0,5	FRA: 99% HALCOR: 88% SIEMENS -	We will extend this evaluation to the SIEMENS use case as well.	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 HALCOR: UC5S1, UC5S2

Table 36: Robust and resilient learning (Strategy 7) – verification of CRV component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Robust and resilient learning (Strategy 7) T4.1	Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence CRV [UNSPMF]	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1: Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum	KPI3.1.1	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	Comparison to baseline methods	Decrease in energy consumption measured in Joules	energy consumption of baseline with full re-training	0,15	On the EDICT dataset (IMT), the decrease in energy consumption for novel MAML methods is 99% compared to the best performing baseline employing complete re-training	Further evaluation of novel methods on PANDORA related datasets with clearly defined tasks	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 PCL: UC3S1, UC3S2 HALCOR: UC5S1, UC5S2

Table 37: Parallel, Distributed & Federated representational learning (Strategy 8) – verification of FRML component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Parallel, Distributed & Federated representational learning (Strategy 8) T4.3	Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations FRML [SAG]	EN1.1: Models, mechanisms, and tools for reliable and optimised data analysis upscale and speed up through federated representation and robust learning	KR1.1: Research advances in distributed, and federated learning approaches for fostering the adoption of trustworthy AI technologies towards delivering robust, efficient, and verifiable AI models that increase intelligence in “data for AI” pipelines across the computing continuum and scale up autonomy in AIoT operations for smart spaces	KPI1.1.1	Increase models accuracy	Performance metrics analysis	f1 score, roc_auc	results for vanilla federated learning auto encoder: F1 = 66%, ROC_AUC = 59%	>= 20%	Relative improvement of memory-augmented autoencoder: F1 = 15%, ROC_AUC = 39%	Proceeding with SIEMENS data set	EAB: UC2S1, SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2
				KPI1.1.2	Number of models trained	Pilot Studies	Number of trained and tested using distributed learning approaches.	1	>= 10	EAB use cases: - UNSPMF: 8 - THALES: 1 SAG us cases: -	Continue proceeding with other use cases / datasets.	EAB: UC2S1, SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2
		EN2.3: Mechanisms, models, and solutions for capturing the necessary information and communicating it through compact data representations	KR2.3: Development of efficient, resilient, robust mechanisms and ML-based tools for the extraction and use of data knowledge, towards creating intelligence data pipelines in reproducing customisable and trustworthy datasets for model training and testing in AIoT deployments	KPI2.3.1	Increased accuracy levels of real-time observations to capture out-of-distribution events	Performance metrics analysis	f1 score	splitting dataset over individual edge nodes (~ f1 accuracy 85% -90%)	federating the training. Expectation: ~ 95 % accuracy	on going development & testing	Work on much larger data sets. Add AutoEncoder memory matrix to approach to improve accuracy improvements.	EAB: UC2S1, SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2
				KPI2.3.2	Number of models deployed across the cloud continuum	Pilot Studies	Number of instances of an AI model deployed	1	≥3	on going development & testing	Deployment of models trained under federated learning	EAB: UC2S1, SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2
		EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based	KR3.2: Encapsulating computing continuum	KPI3.1.2	Accuracy of federated learning methods, subject	Performance metrics analysis	f1 score, roc_auc	results for vanilla federated learning auto encoder: F1	>= 70%	results of memory-augmented autoencoder: F1 =	Work with other datasets	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2, PCL: UC3S1, UC3S2

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		methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	infrastructure and characteristics for optimising the lifecycle management of "data in AI" pipelines, ensuring efficient and trustworthy AI processes in the selection, deployment, inference and re-training of relevant data products		to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics			F = 66%, ROC_AUC = 59%		76%, ROC_AUC = 82%		FRA: UC4S1, UC4S2
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Table 38: Continuous, explainable and domain-informed AI (Strategy 9) – verification of DICE component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Continuous, explainable and domain-informed AI (Strategy 9) T4.2	Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning DICE [CYU]	EN2.4: A tool-based explainable AI and interpretation modelling framework for domain knowledge	KR2.2: Analysis of existing domain knowledge, and experimental datasets, simulation models and tools	KPI2.4.1	Number of improved properties characterising the quality of the provided explanations of continuous and domain-informed AI decisions >= 2	Performance metrics analysis Number of explanation properties improved.	Metric corresponding to each property. For instance, proximity for counterfactual explanations can be measured by the average of the L2 measure of the distance between the new and the old point. Consiceness can be measured by the number of changed properties.	0	>=2 improved properties	on going development & testing	Further research for developing explainability methods for the various use cases. Further experiments with the data of the use cases.	SAG: UC1S1 EAB: UC2S2 FRA: UC4S1 HALCOR: UC5S1

Table 39: Continual Deep Learning (Strategy 10) – verification of CIM component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Continual Deep Learning (Strategy 10) T4.4	Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models CIM [AU]	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1: Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum	KPI3.1.3	Decrease in the response time for AI models inference	Performance metrics analysis Model speedup	FLOPS, Inference time	1x	1.2x	on going development & testing	Further research for faster models	EAB: UC2S1, UC2S2 HALCOR: UC5S1, UC5S

Table 40: Split Deep Learning (Strategy 11) – verification of ADOA component

Pandora Strategies Task	Components	Enabler	KR definition	KPI id	KPI definition	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	Follow-up Actions	UC
Split Deep Learning (Strategy 11) T4.5	Adaptive distribution and optimization of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing continuum ADOA [NTUA]	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1: Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum	KPI 2.2.2	Reduction in model execution time	Performance metrics analysis Optimal inference execution times based on NN model placement. Implementation of a NN distribution algorithm and a model placement mechanism based on the profiling of devices within the cluster.	Inference time. Comparison of inference times between random model placement (t1) and a profiling-based model placement (t2).	Not a specific base value. Decreased inference times using the profiling-based model placement mechanism.	t2 < t1	Average placement accuracy of profiler: 98.63%. Average placement accuracy of randomly placing models: 31.16%. Decrease in model execution time and response time: 60%	Improved model splitting algorithm and research on profiling mechanisms. Perform model placement based on more variables.	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 EAB: UC2S1, UC2S2
				KPI 3.1.3	Decrease in the response time for AI models inference	Performance metrics analysis Optimal inference execution times based on NN model placement. Implementation of a NN distribution algorithm and a model placement mechanism based on the profiling of devices within the cluster.	Inference time. Comparison of inference times between random model placement (t1) and a profiling-based model placement (t2).	The execution of the original model in commodity machines. Decreased inference times using the profiling-based model placement mechanism.	t2 < t1	Average placement accuracy of profiler: 98.63%. Average placement accuracy of randomly placing models: 31.16%. Decrease in model execution time and response time: 60%	Improved model splitting algorithm and research on profiling mechanisms. Perform model placement based on more variables.	SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 EAB: UC2S1, UC2S2

D6.1 – Instantiation of PANDORA pipelines in industrial settings

GA No. 101135775

			<p>KR3.2: Encapsulating computing continuum infrastructure characteristics in optimising the lifecycle management of "data in AI" pipelines, ensuring efficient and trustworthy AI processes in the selection, deployment, inference and re-training of relevant data products</p>	<p>KPI 2.3.2 Number of models deployed across the cloud continuum</p>	<p>Pilot Studies Trained profiler that yields optimal placement across the cloud continuum on 11 models. Then the model is split into independent submodels that are allocated to resources based on their profile.</p>	<p>Number of submodels that ADOA can deploy for each trained model, achieving ±5% the same level of accuracy as the original model in suitable resources</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>>=3</p>	<p>Accurate placement of 4 submodels in UC2S1</p>	<p>Deploy more models across the cloud continuum and test on a larger number of devices</p>	<p>SAG: UC1S1, UC1S2 EAB: UC2S1, UC2S2</p>
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7 Conclusions

Deliverable 6.1 (Instantiation of PANDORA pipelines in industrial settings) documents the work conducted within WP6 during months M09-M18 of the PANDORA project, focusing on the preparatory activities and pipeline instantiation across Tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 6.4 and 6.5. This deliverable establishes the methodological, architectural, and regulatory foundations necessary for real-life experimentation and validation of PANDORA's trustworthy AI mechanisms across five industrial sectors.

The integrated approach developed for Tasks 6.1 and 6.2 represents a key methodological contribution, consolidating business and validation scenario alignment with technical pipeline instantiation into unified documentation templates. This integration addresses the challenge of creating a generic yet adaptable framework suitable for five heterogeneous industrial pilots operating in different sectors (nuclear energy, smart buildings, manufacturing, healthcare, robotics) with distinct data sources, regulatory requirements, and operational environments.

Five data pipeline blueprint templates have been developed and completed, one for each pilot use case: SAG (Industrial Edge network optimization), Ericsson/EAB (5G-enabled smart building robotics), PCL (visual quality inspection), FRA (hydrogen refueling station predictive maintenance) and HALCOR (manufacturing energy consumption forecasting). Each template documents:

- **Use case context:** business sector descriptions, operational environments, hardware/software configurations, data requirements, and key business KPIs
- **Contributing strategies and components:** mapping of PANDORA Phase 1 components (tSDG/vSDG, QU-MAD, DEL, DACL, DRFE) and Phase 2 components (FRLM, ADOA, CRV, DICE, CIM) to specific scenarios
- **Generic pipeline architecture:** interactions between AlaaS, CaaS, and IM with detailed component specifications including tools, input/output data formats, and dependencies
- **Scenario-specific adaptations:** documentation of component application status, implementation challenges, and deviations from initial plans

The verification and validation framework established in Task 6.3 (led by NTUA) provides systematic KPI mapping that links performance metrics to PANDORA strategies, components, and use case scenarios. This framework defines verification and validation variables (both independent and dependent) that will enable objective assessment of PANDORA's performance for Phase 1 (trustworthy dataset generation) and Phase 2 (autonomous AIoT operations). The early initiation of this task ensured that validation considerations were integrated into pipeline design from the beginning.

Regulatory compliance and data protection frameworks have been established for all pilots, addressing GDPR requirements, sector-specific regulations, data minimization protocols, anonymization procedures, access control mechanisms, and cybersecurity measures. This ensures experimental activities can proceed within appropriate legal and ethical boundaries while maintaining stakeholder trust.

Tutorial development (KPI3.4.1 and KPI3.4.2) supports knowledge transfer and competence building by providing guidance on template completion, component mapping, and pipeline instantiation. Iterative feedback from pilot partners (EAB, STUBA, NTUA, project leaders, Eunomia) has been incorporated through multiple modification cycles to ensure tutorials effectively enable partners to operationalize PANDORA components.

Task 6.1/6.2: Partners finalized their pilot-specific templates by providing detailed component integration specifications in collaboration with technical leads from WP3, WP4, and WP5. The five pipeline blueprints will be validated through initial deployment experiences of task 6.3.

Task 6.3: The verification and validation framework will be operationalized as component implementations mature and pilot datasets stabilize.

Task 6.4: Led by PCL CL, operational deployment will transition from planning to active experimentation. Phase 1 (offline) will validate synthetic and enhanced datasets against real-world data and domain knowledge to ensure combined datasets (real + synthetic) perform as intended. Phase 2 (online) will deploy Intelligence Data Pipelines supporting continuous, energy-efficient, and robust AIoT operations in industrial environments, executing the five experiments defined for each pilot.

Task 6.5: Led by NTUA, quantifiable progress assessment and impact analysis will commence, establishing baseline measurements for multidisciplinary domain expert evaluations. Progress will be monitored against societal, academic, and industry-validated benchmarks to demonstrate PANDORA's contributions to trustworthy AI adoption, energy efficiency improvements, and operational autonomy.

The challenges documented in Section 5 (Problems/Proposed Solutions) highlight the iterative nature of industrial AI deployment: creating adaptable templates for heterogeneous requirements, coordinating across multiple disciplines and work packages, managing dataset availability and quality issues, and aligning evolving component implementations with use case needs. The solutions implemented modular template structures, staged coordination approaches, and flexible adaptation mechanisms demonstrate WP6's pragmatic approach to managing complexity in real-world industrial settings.

The work documented in D6.1 demonstrates PANDORA's readiness to progress from architectural planning and component development to operational deployment and real-world validation. The integrated templates, architectural blueprints, and validation frameworks provide the foundation for systematic experimentation that will demonstrate PANDORA's scientific and industrial impact in achieving Objective 4: providing a cross-sector and multi-variant smart data space that validates trustworthy, energy-efficient AI mechanisms in real-life scenarios across multiple industrial domains.

8 References

[1] D2.2, PANDORA deliverable Architecture and Technical Specifications, 2